

Trends and Determinants of Maternal Death in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital
(2019-2024), Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the trends and determinants of maternal mortality at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), aiming to provide evidence-based insights into maternal health challenges. The primary objective is to analyze patterns of maternal deaths and identify key contributing factors.

Existing research highlights gaps in understanding the specific influences of healthcare infrastructure, socioeconomic disparities, and policy interventions on maternal mortality. This study builds on the health system approach and the Three Delays Model to explore the critical determinants of maternal deaths in a hospital setting.

A retrospective study design was employed, utilizing hospital records from 2019 to 2024. The study population consists of maternal mortality cases at LASUTH, with data collected through hospital records. A purposive sampling technique was used, and data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

Key findings reveal that hemorrhage, hypertensive disorders, and sepsis are the leading direct causes of maternal deaths at LASUTH. Socioeconomic factors such as low education levels, late healthcare-seeking behavior, and financial constraints also play a significant role. The study highlights systemic issues, including delays in accessing emergency obstetric care and inadequacies in healthcare infrastructure.

The study concludes that targeted interventions in emergency obstetric services and maternal health education are crucial to reducing maternal mortality. It recommends strengthening healthcare systems, enhancing community awareness programs, and improving policy implementation to address maternal health challenges effectively.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EmONC	Emergency Obstetric and Neonatal Care
LASUTH	Lagos State University Teaching Hospital
MMR	Maternal Mortality Ratio
NHI	The National Health Insurance Scheme
PHC	Primary Health Care Centre
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TBA	Traditional Birth Attendant
WHO	World Health Organization

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

At the turn of the millennium, maternal mortality gained global attention following the establishment of the Millennium Development Goals in 2000.¹ By 2015, the global Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) had declined by nearly one third, marking a tangible achievement in maternal health on a global scale.³ In 2015, the Sustainable Development Goals ushered in a new era, committing nations to end preventable maternal deaths and aim for an MMR of less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030.⁵ Recent data from global monitoring efforts reports that the world's MMR fell from approximately 380 per 100,000 live births in 2000 to 197 per 100,000 live births by 2020, a 48 percent decline (add ref). While this marks progress, the pace remains insufficient. SDG targets require an annual MMR decline rate of 14.8 percent, yet the current global pace is estimated at only 1.6 percent. At this rate, the goal of reducing MMR to 70 by 2030 is unlikely to be met.⁶

Despite the decline in MMR in many countries of the world, mortality rates remain high in nine countries, including Nigeria, India, Pakistan, and the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Sub Saharan Africa alone accounted for nearly 70 percent of global maternal fatalities, while South Asia contributed around 20 percent. The Central African Republic, with an MMR of 1,150, and Sierra Leone, at 1,120, showcase the enormity of the challenge in fragile settings.⁷ Nigeria accounts for one of the highest maternal mortality ratios (MMR) globally, contributing significantly to the global burden. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 20%–30% of all maternal deaths worldwide occur in Nigeria (add ref). This staggering statistic underscores the critical need to examine the root causes, trends, and interventions related to maternal deaths within the country.⁸ Trends from NDHS and WHO data reveal a pattern of persistently

high maternal mortality rates. While there was a slight improvement from the estimates in NDHS 2008 (545 per 100,000)⁹, the changes have not been significant enough to signal a breakthrough. Furthermore, disparities across regions and populations complicate the national picture. Maternal mortality in the northern regions of Nigeria tends to be higher than in the south, attributed to differences in health-seeking behavior, education, and access to care.¹⁰

States like Lagos have made strides in enrolling citizens and upgrading facilities, but maternal health issues persist in many parts of the state particularly in the urban slum.¹¹ Achieving the SDG target requires multi-sectorial action, community engagement, and political will. Lagos State University Teaching Hospital as a leading tertiary hospital, records numerous maternal deaths, yet comprehensive data on trends and underlying determinants remain scarce.¹² Understanding why maternal deaths persist despite existing healthcare interventions is essential for policy formulation and effective maternal health strategies.¹³

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Maternal mortality remains unacceptably high in Nigeria, with thousands of preventable deaths recorded annually. The Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2018 estimates the maternal mortality ratio at 512 per 100,000 live births.¹⁴ Despite some improvements since the early 2000s, Nigeria remains off-track in achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3.1, which aims to reduce global MMR to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030.¹⁵

Direct medical causes remain the leading contributors to maternal mortality in Nigeria. Hemorrhage, particularly postpartum hemorrhage, is cited as the primary cause of

maternal death.¹⁶ Hypertensive disorders such as pre-eclampsia and eclampsia also account for a significant proportion. Infections (notably sepsis), complications from unsafe abortions, and obstructed labor are other critical causes.¹⁷ Indirect causes include pre-existing conditions exacerbated by pregnancy, such as anemia, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria.¹⁸ These conditions, when not adequately managed during antenatal care or delivery, can result in fatal outcomes. Moreover, many women in Nigeria do not have access to timely or adequate prenatal, intrapartum, or postpartum care that can help mitigate these risks.¹⁹

In addition to national-level data, there exist significant sub-national inequalities in maternal mortality, especially in south-west Nigeria and within urban slum communities in Lagos State:

1. A community-based study in Lagos using the indirect sisterhood method found an MMR of 430 per 100,000 live births.²⁰
2. In two of Lagos's most disadvantaged urban slums (Makoko Riverine and Badia East), Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) estimated an even higher MMR of 1,050 per 100,000 live births.²¹
3. The lifetime risk of maternal death in these slum communities was also very high: 1 in 18.²²

These data demonstrate how aggregate national statistics can mask severe local disparities. Marginalized populations, such as those in urban slums, face disproportionately higher maternal mortality, likely due to poor access to quality care, socioeconomic vulnerabilities, and systemic inequities.²³

Nigeria's maternal mortality burden is strongly influenced by socioeconomic determinants. Low levels of education among women, especially in the northern states, correlate with limited knowledge about pregnancy risks and reduced healthcare utilization.²⁴ Early

marriage and teenage pregnancies are prevalent in several regions, often leading to complications due to physiological immaturity and social disempowerment.²⁵ Poverty is a significant barrier to accessing quality maternal healthcare. In rural areas, the absence of healthcare infrastructure, coupled with the cost of transportation and services, discourages women from seeking institutional care. Cultural and religious beliefs also shape maternal health outcomes. In some communities, male family members make healthcare decisions, limiting women's autonomy in seeking care.²⁶

1.3 Justification of the Study

Maternal mortality remains a significant global public health challenge and serves as a critical indicator of the effectiveness of a country's healthcare system, particularly regarding reproductive and maternal health services²⁷. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), an estimated 287,000 women died in 2020 due to complications related to pregnancy and childbirth; deaths that are overwhelmingly preventable through timely and effective medical interventions²⁸. Documenting the recent data in a tertiary hospital will be plausible for planning.²⁹

SDG 3.1 aims to reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030, with no country having an MMR above 140³⁰. At its current rate, Nigeria is unlikely to meet this target without accelerated interventions. Understanding the trends and determinants of maternal mortality at LASUTH is vital for developing targeted interventions. As a tertiary referral hospital handling a high volume of high-risk pregnancies, LASUTH provides a valuable context for analyzing maternal health outcomes. A review of maternal deaths between 2019 and 2024 can reveal important patterns and root causes, ranging from medical conditions like hypertensive disorders and hemorrhage to social determinants like education, poverty, and delayed access to care.

Additionally, examining institutional factors; staffing levels, emergency response capacity, referral efficiency, documentation practices, and availability of critical resources; can inform strategies for improving tertiary-level maternal care. A thorough analysis of both individual and systemic contributors to maternal mortality is essential for achieving sustainable improvements.

1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the trends and determinants of maternal deaths at LASUTH.

Objectives:

1. Describe the age distribution of maternal deaths at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.
2. Examine the trend of maternal mortality at LASUTH from 2019 to 2024 using available hospital records.
3. Assess the association between institutional factors; such as referral status, timing of care, and place of delivery, and maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.
4. Identify the key clinical and demographic determinants contributing to maternal deaths at LASUTH during the study period.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What has been the trend of maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024?
2. What is the age pattern of maternal deaths recorded at LASUTH during the study period?
3. How are institutional factors; such as referral patterns, timing of admission, and place of delivery, associated with maternal mortality at LASUTH?

4. What major determinants contribute to maternal deaths at LASUTH, based on hospital data from 2019 to 2024?

1.6 Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1 (Institutional Factors & Maternal Mortality)

H₀₁: There is no significant association between institutional factors (referral status, timing of admission, and place of delivery) and maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.

H₁₁: There is a significant association between institutional factors and maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.

Hypothesis 2 (Demographic/Clinical Determinants & Maternal Mortality)

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between selected demographic/clinical determinants (maternal age, gestational age, parity) and maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.

H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between selected demographic/clinical determinants and maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024.

Hypothesis 3 Temporal Variation in Maternal Mortality (2019–2024)

There is no significant change in the trend of maternal mortality at LASUTH from 2019 to 2024.

H₁₃: There is a significant change in the trend of maternal mortality at LASUTH from 2019 to 2024.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study holds significant importance as it provides a comprehensive, evidence-based analysis of maternal mortality trends and determinants at one of Nigeria's leading tertiary health institutions; Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH). The findings will contribute to a deeper understanding of the medical, systemic, and socio-economic factors influencing maternal health outcomes in an urban, resource-constrained setting. This is crucial for identifying actionable gaps in healthcare delivery, clinical protocols, and institutional readiness to handle high-risk pregnancies and obstetric emergencies.

The study is expected to inform healthcare policymakers at the state and national levels by offering robust data that can shape health policy formulation and resource allocation.

Understanding the trends and root causes of maternal mortality over a ten-year period allows for the design of targeted interventions that are both timely and contextually appropriate. Policymakers can use this evidence to justify investments in healthcare infrastructure, training of skilled birth attendants, and the development of maternal health programs that address local realities in Lagos and similar urban areas.

Healthcare providers and hospital administrators at LASUTH will benefit from the study through insights that may improve service delivery, emergency response times, referral systems, and the availability of essential maternal health resources. The results can guide internal audits, staff performance reviews, and quality improvement initiatives.

Identifying patterns in maternal deaths; whether linked to delays, clinical mismanagement, or systemic inefficiencies; can lead to the development of protocols that mitigate preventable deaths and enhance patient outcomes.

Beyond institutional benefits, the study has the potential to contribute to community-level awareness and behavior change. Findings may be used to advocate for maternal health education campaigns that empower women and families to recognize danger signs during

pregnancy and seek timely care. By highlighting social determinants such as education, income, and access to transportation, the study can support community-based solutions and advocacy efforts to reduce delays in care and overcome health-seeking barriers. Finally, the study adds academic value by filling a critical gap in the maternal health literature in Nigeria. Localized, longitudinal studies on maternal mortality remain scarce, especially those based on tertiary hospital data. This research will serve as a reference point for future studies, foster academic discourse, and potentially inform curriculum development for public health training. In alignment with Sustainable Development Goal 3.1, which aims to reduce maternal mortality globally, the study's findings can contribute to Nigeria's progress in achieving international health targets and fostering equity in maternal health outcomes.

1.10 Operational Definition of Terms

1.10.1 Maternal Mortality.

Maternal mortality refers to the death of a woman while she is pregnant or within 42 days of the termination of pregnancy, regardless of the pregnancy's duration or site, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management, excluding accidental or incidental causes. This definition is grounded in the World Health Organization (WHO) classification and underscores the importance of focusing on direct and indirect obstetric causes, such as complications from hemorrhage, eclampsia, sepsis, unsafe abortion, or inadequate care during labor and delivery. Maternal mortality serves as a critical indicator of the performance of a health system, particularly in maternal and reproductive healthcare.

1.10.2 Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR).

The Maternal Mortality Ratio is defined as the number of maternal deaths per 100,000 live births in a given time period, typically within a year. This measure is used globally to assess and compare the effectiveness, accessibility, and safety of maternal healthcare systems. A high MMR often signals systemic challenges in healthcare infrastructure, skilled birth attendance, emergency response capacity, and social determinants such as poverty and education. For example, an MMR of 512 in Nigeria suggests that for every 100,000 live births, 512 women die from pregnancy-related causes; a significantly high figure compared to the global target of less than 70 by 2030 under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3.1).

1.10.3 Skilled Birth Attendant (SBA).

A Skilled Birth Attendant is a health professional; such as a midwife, nurse, or doctor; who has been trained and is certified to manage uncomplicated pregnancies and deliveries, as well as to detect, manage, or refer complications during the antenatal, intrapartum, and postpartum periods. SBAs are central to reducing maternal mortality because they ensure that critical health interventions are administered promptly and correctly. In practice, the presence of a skilled attendant can significantly reduce the risks of hemorrhage, infection, and other life-threatening complications. However, the mere presence of a skilled provider is not enough; there must also be enabling conditions such as proper equipment, medications, referral systems, and institutional support.

1.10.4 Emergency Obstetric Care (EmOC).

Emergency Obstetric Care refers to a set of life-saving medical interventions required to manage complications during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. EmOC is typically classified into two levels: Basic EmOC (BEmOC) and Comprehensive EmOC

(CEmOC). Basic care includes functions like administering parenteral antibiotics and oxytocics, manual removal of placenta, and assisted vaginal delivery. Comprehensive care expands to include surgical capabilities such as cesarean sections and blood transfusions. EmOC is essential for addressing the most common direct causes of maternal death, including postpartum hemorrhage, obstructed labor, hypertensive disorders, and sepsis. The availability and accessibility of EmOC services are strong determinants of maternal survival, especially in referral hospitals like LASUTH, where high-risk pregnancies are frequently managed.

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CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Maternal mortality is a critical public health issue that continues to affect many countries worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income regions. Defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the death of a woman during pregnancy, childbirth, or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, maternal mortality encompasses a broad range of causes.¹ These causes include direct obstetric complications, such as hemorrhage, eclampsia, and sepsis, as well as indirect factors, such as pre-existing health conditions that are worsened by pregnancy.² Although maternal mortality rates have decreased globally over the past few decades, the rates in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly Nigeria, remain disproportionately high.³

Nigeria's maternal mortality rate (MMR) is one of the highest in the world, standing at 512 deaths per 100,000 live births in recent estimates.⁴ This stark figure highlights the urgent need to address the underlying determinants of maternal mortality in the country. The conceptual understanding of maternal mortality encompasses a complex interplay of medical, socio-economic, cultural, and healthcare system factors.⁵ By exploring the key variables that contribute to maternal mortality, this review seeks to provide a clearer understanding of the various components that influence maternal health outcomes in Nigeria.⁶

2.1.1 Maternal Mortality

Maternal mortality is a critical indicator of the overall health and well-being of a population, reflecting both the availability and quality of healthcare services, as well as broader socio-economic factors. It is defined as the death of a woman during pregnancy, childbirth, or within 42 days of the termination of pregnancy, due to complications directly or indirectly related to the pregnancy or its management.⁷ However, maternal mortality does not include deaths caused by accidental or incidental factors, such as injuries from accidents or violent acts. In global health discussions, maternal mortality is considered a fundamental measure of the effectiveness of a country's healthcare system, particularly in terms of maternal health services, obstetric care, and the availability of timely interventions.⁸

2.1.2 Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR)

The maternal mortality ratio (MMR) is the most common statistical measure used to assess maternal mortality rates in a population. It is calculated as the number of maternal deaths per 100,000 live births in a given year. This metric is crucial for tracking trends in maternal health and is widely used by global health organizations, including the World Health Organization (WHO), to compare maternal health outcomes across countries and regions.⁹ In the case of Nigeria, the MMR remains one of the highest globally, with estimates indicating that approximately 512 women die per 100,000 live births.¹⁰ This rate places Nigeria among the top countries with the highest maternal mortality, despite global efforts to reduce these figures through international health initiatives.

A closer examination of the MMR in Nigeria reveals significant regional and socio-economic disparities. For example, maternal mortality rates in rural areas tend to be much

higher than in urban centers, due to factors such as limited access to healthcare, lack of skilled birth attendants, and delayed medical interventions.¹¹ The urban-rural divide underscores the need for targeted healthcare interventions that focus on improving access to quality maternal care in underserved regions.

2.1.3 Classification of Maternal Deaths

Maternal mortality is typically classified into **direct** and **indirect causes**. These classifications help identify the specific risks that contribute to maternal deaths and provide insights into which areas of maternal healthcare need improvement.¹²

Direct Maternal Deaths.

Direct maternal deaths are those that arise from complications during pregnancy, childbirth, or the postpartum period, which are directly caused by obstetric complications, interventions, omissions, or incorrect treatment. These complications can often be prevented or managed with timely and appropriate medical care. Some of the most common causes of direct maternal deaths include.¹

- 1. Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH).** This is one of the leading causes of maternal death worldwide and remains a significant contributor to maternal mortality in Nigeria. PPH refers to excessive bleeding after childbirth, which can be life-threatening if not managed promptly.¹⁴ The lack of adequate blood transfusion facilities and skilled birth attendants in many regions exacerbates the risks associated with PPH.
- 2. Eclampsia and Pre-eclampsia.** Eclampsia, which involves the onset of seizures during pregnancy, and pre-eclampsia, a condition characterized by high blood pressure and organ damage, are major causes of maternal deaths. These conditions can be fatal if left untreated, but their progression can be mitigated with regular antenatal care and timely

medical intervention, such as the administration of antihypertensive medication and magnesium sulfate.

3. Obstructed Labour. This occurs when the fetus is unable to pass through the birth canal due to factors such as fetal malpresentation, maternal pelvic abnormalities, or inadequate maternal contractions. Without timely medical intervention, obstructed labor can lead to serious complications, including uterine rupture and maternal sepsis.

4. Sepsis and Infections. Maternal infections, particularly those arising from unsanitary conditions during childbirth or from untreated infections such as urinary tract infections and sexually transmitted diseases, can lead to life-threatening sepsis. Poor hygiene practices, lack of proper sterilization of medical equipment, and insufficient infection control measures in healthcare facilities contribute to high rates of infection-related maternal deaths.

Indirect Maternal Deaths

Indirect maternal deaths, on the other hand, occur due to pre-existing medical conditions that are worsened by pregnancy. These conditions may not be directly related to obstetric complications, but pregnancy can exacerbate underlying health issues, leading to maternal mortality. Common indirect causes include.

1. Malaria. Malaria is a leading cause of maternal mortality in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria. The disease is exacerbated during pregnancy, leading to complications such as anemia, miscarriage, and preterm birth. Malaria can also increase the likelihood of severe maternal morbidity, including maternal death if not properly managed.¹⁵

2. **HIV/AIDS.** HIV is another major indirect cause of maternal mortality in Nigeria.

Pregnant women living with HIV are at increased risk of complications such as opportunistic infections, which can lead to maternal death. Lack of access to antiretroviral therapy (ART) and maternal-child transmission prevention programs further exacerbates these risks.

3. **Cardiovascular Diseases.** Pre-existing cardiovascular conditions, such as hypertension and heart disease, can be aggravated by pregnancy, leading to severe complications like heart failure and stroke. With insufficient medical care and monitoring, women with cardiovascular issues may face a significantly higher risk of maternal mortality.

4. **Diabetes and Kidney Disease.** Both pre-existing diabetes and kidney disease can worsen during pregnancy. Uncontrolled diabetes, for example, can increase the risk of preterm labor, fetal malformations, and maternal complications such as pre-eclampsia and infection.¹⁶

Influence of Socio-Economic and Healthcare Access

The high rates of maternal mortality in Nigeria are significantly influenced by socio-economic factors, particularly healthcare access. Women in poverty-stricken areas often face substantial barriers to accessing skilled obstetric care, which increases the risks of complications during pregnancy and childbirth. Poor infrastructure, inadequate healthcare financing,¹⁶ and a lack of trained healthcare professionals further hinder access to timely and effective care.

In addition, socio-economic disparities such as education level, early marriage, and gender inequality contribute to maternal mortality. Women with lower levels of education are less likely to seek antenatal care or deliver in healthcare facilities, instead opting for home births with unskilled attendants, which increases the risk of complications.

Furthermore, early marriage and adolescent pregnancies, which remain common in some parts of Nigeria, present higher risks of maternal death due to the physical immaturity of young mothers.

Global and National Responses

In response to the persistently high maternal mortality rates in Nigeria, national and international efforts have been implemented to address the root causes of maternal deaths. These initiatives include strengthening the healthcare system, improving access to family planning services, and increasing the number of skilled birth attendants in rural areas. However, despite these efforts, maternal mortality remains a significant challenge due to persistent gaps in healthcare delivery, cultural barriers, and inadequate resources.

International agencies, such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF, continue to support maternal health programs aimed at reducing maternal deaths.¹⁷ These programs include the provision of financial and technical support for maternal health interventions, training healthcare workers, and improving the availability of essential drugs and medical supplies.

2.1.4 The Role of Socio-Economic and Cultural Factors

The socio-economic environment plays a significant role in shaping maternal health outcomes. Maternal mortality is a multidimensional issue influenced by poverty, education, cultural norms, and healthcare accessibility. These factors determine whether a woman receives adequate medical care during pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum. Addressing socio-economic and cultural barriers is critical in reducing maternal mortality rates, particularly in countries like Nigeria, where maternal health disparities remain a pressing concern.

Economic Barriers and Financial Constraints

Poverty remains one of the most significant determinants of maternal mortality. Women from lower-income households are less likely to access quality maternal healthcare services due to financial constraints. Many healthcare facilities require out-of-pocket payments for services such as antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and emergency obstetric care, making it difficult for economically disadvantaged women to afford essential medical support. This financial burden often forces women to rely on traditional birth attendants (TBAs) or delay seeking formal medical assistance when complications arise.¹⁸ Delayed or inadequate medical intervention can result in fatal outcomes for both mother and child.

The economic challenges are even more pronounced in rural areas, where healthcare infrastructure is often lacking. Many rural health facilities are understaffed, under-equipped, and located far from communities, making access difficult for pregnant women. Transportation costs further exacerbate the issue, as many women are unable to afford the expense of traveling to healthcare centers, particularly in emergency situations. The lack of ambulance services and poor road conditions increase the likelihood of maternal deaths due to delays in receiving urgent care.

Government policies on healthcare financing also play a crucial role in determining maternal health outcomes. In Nigeria, initiatives such as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) have aimed to improve healthcare access, but coverage remains low, particularly among rural and low-income populations.¹⁹ Expanding health insurance coverage and introducing free or subsidized maternal healthcare services could significantly reduce financial barriers to accessing quality maternal care.

Education and Maternal Health Outcomes

Education is another crucial socio-economic determinant of maternal health. Women with higher levels of education are more likely to seek professional healthcare services during pregnancy and childbirth. Education enhances women's awareness of the importance of antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and postnatal check-ups. It also enables them to recognize potential pregnancy complications and take appropriate action to prevent adverse outcomes.

Studies have shown that increasing women's access to education significantly reduces maternal mortality rates. Educated women are more likely to use contraceptives, engage in family planning, and space their pregnancies appropriately, thereby reducing high-risk pregnancies. Furthermore, education empowers women to challenge harmful traditional practices and make informed decisions regarding their reproductive health.

However, gender disparities in education remain a major challenge in many developing countries, including Nigeria. In some regions, particularly in the northern states, cultural and economic factors contribute to low female literacy rates. Many girls are withdrawn from school at an early age due to financial constraints, preference for male education, or the expectation that they will marry young.²⁰ This lack of education not only limits their economic opportunities but also restricts their ability to make informed health decisions, ultimately contributing to higher maternal mortality rates.

Investing in female education and promoting literacy programs can have a profound impact on maternal health. Policies that support girls' education, discourage early marriage, and provide vocational training opportunities can help break the cycle of poverty and improve maternal and child health outcomes.

Early Marriage and Adolescent Pregnancies

Early marriage and adolescent pregnancies significantly contribute to maternal mortality. In Nigeria, child marriage remains prevalent, with many girls married off before the age of 18. Early marriage often leads to early pregnancy, which poses serious health risks for both the mother and the baby.²¹ Young girls' bodies are not fully developed for childbirth, making them more susceptible to complications such as obstructed labor, preeclampsia, and postpartum hemorrhage.

Adolescent pregnancies are associated with higher risks of maternal death, as young mothers are less likely to access skilled medical care. Many teenage mothers lack knowledge about proper prenatal care and often delay seeking medical attention during pregnancy. Furthermore, social stigma and cultural norms may discourage young mothers from attending health facilities, increasing the likelihood of birth-related complications.

Addressing early marriage and adolescent pregnancies requires a multi-faceted approach, including strict enforcement of child marriage laws, increased educational opportunities for girls, and community awareness programs. Providing comprehensive sexual and reproductive health education can also help reduce adolescent pregnancies and improve maternal health outcomes.

Cultural Beliefs and Traditional Practices

Cultural beliefs and practices play a pivotal role in shaping maternal health outcomes. In many Nigerian communities, childbirth is perceived as a natural process that does not necessarily require medical intervention. As a result, some women prefer to deliver at home with the assistance of traditional birth attendants rather than seeking care from trained healthcare professionals. While TBAs may offer valuable emotional support, they

often lack the necessary skills to handle obstetric complications, leading to preventable maternal deaths.²²

Certain cultural norms also discourage the use of modern maternal healthcare services. For instance, some communities believe that labor pain should be endured without medical assistance, leading to resistance toward pain relief or surgical interventions such as cesarean sections.²³ Similarly, misconceptions about hospital births, such as fears of exposure to evil spirits or beliefs that hospitals are only for severely ill patients, discourage women from seeking institutional deliveries.

Harmful traditional practices, such as female genital mutilation (FGM), further increase maternal health risks. Women who have undergone FGM are more likely to experience prolonged labor, perineal tears, and obstetric fistulas due to scarring and narrowing of the birth canal. Despite global and national efforts to eliminate FGM, the practice persists in some Nigerian communities, endangering the health and lives of women and newborns.²⁴

Overcoming these cultural barriers requires community engagement and education. Health professionals, religious leaders, and community elders must be involved in efforts to promote safe childbirth practices. Implementing culturally sensitive maternal health programs and training TBAs to work alongside skilled birth attendants can help bridge the gap between traditional and modern healthcare practices.

2.1.5 Healthcare System Factors

The quality and accessibility of the healthcare system are central to reducing maternal mortality. A well-functioning healthcare system ensures that pregnant women receive timely medical attention, skilled delivery care, and appropriate postnatal services.

However, in many low-resource settings, including Nigeria, significant healthcare system challenges hinder efforts to improve maternal health outcomes.

Shortage of Skilled Healthcare Personnel

One of the primary determinants of maternal deaths is the availability of skilled healthcare personnel, particularly trained midwives and obstetricians. Skilled birth attendants play a crucial role in preventing complications during pregnancy and childbirth, providing essential interventions such as timely cesarean sections, management of postpartum hemorrhage, and neonatal resuscitation.²⁵ However, in Nigeria, there is a significant shortage of skilled birth attendants, especially in rural areas. According to the Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (2018), more than 40% of births still occur without the assistance of a skilled professional, increasing the risks of complications during childbirth.²⁶

The unequal distribution of healthcare workers between urban and rural areas further exacerbates this issue. Many trained professionals prefer to work in urban centers where infrastructure and working conditions are better, leaving rural areas underserved. This disparity means that many women in remote communities have limited access to skilled birth attendants, increasing their vulnerability to preventable maternal deaths.

Additionally, poor working conditions, low wages, and lack of incentives discourage healthcare workers from remaining in the public sector, leading to further shortages.

Inadequate Healthcare Infrastructure

The lack of well-equipped healthcare facilities is another major contributor to maternal mortality. Many health centers, particularly in rural areas, lack essential medical equipment, drugs, and supplies needed for safe deliveries. Maternity wards often operate

without functional operating theaters, blood banks, or intensive care units, making it difficult to handle obstetric emergencies effectively. Women experiencing complications such as obstructed labor, postpartum hemorrhage, or eclampsia require immediate medical intervention, but the absence of adequate infrastructure increases the likelihood of fatal outcomes.²⁷

Additionally, many primary healthcare centers do not have 24-hour services or emergency obstetric care, leaving pregnant women at risk if they experience complications at night or during weekends. Even when referral hospitals exist, many are overburdened with patients, leading to delays in receiving critical care. The situation is worsened by frequent power outages, lack of clean water, and inadequate infection control measures, all of which compromise the quality of maternal healthcare services.

Barriers to Accessing Healthcare Facilities

Geographic and transportation challenges also play a significant role in maternal mortality. In rural regions, women often face difficulties accessing healthcare facilities due to long distances, poor road conditions, and limited transportation options. Many communities do not have functioning ambulance services, making it difficult for women to reach hospitals in time during emergencies. Instead, they rely on makeshift transportation, such as motorcycles or carts, which are not only slow but also unsafe for pregnant women experiencing complications.²⁸

Delayed access to healthcare facilities contributes to the "three delays model", a framework used to explain maternal deaths.²⁹ The first delay occurs when families take too long to recognize danger signs and decide to seek medical help. The second delay happens due to challenges in reaching a healthcare facility, and the third delay arises from

inefficiencies within the hospital system, such as long wait times or inadequate medical staff. These delays significantly increase the risk of maternal mortality, particularly for women who require urgent medical intervention.

Healthcare Financing and Maternal Health Services

Healthcare financing is another key factor influencing maternal health outcomes.

Although Nigeria has made some strides in healthcare financing through initiatives like the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), funding for maternal health remains inadequate.³⁰ Many women, especially those in low-income households, cannot afford the costs associated with antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, or emergency obstetric care. Out-of-pocket expenses for medical services, drugs, and transportation pose a significant barrier, preventing many pregnant women from accessing essential healthcare services.

Despite global recommendations for increased government investment in maternal healthcare, Nigeria's healthcare budget allocation remains low. Many public hospitals and primary healthcare centers struggle with underfunding, leading to shortages in medical supplies, poorly maintained facilities, and insufficient staffing. Expanding health insurance coverage and introducing free or subsidized maternal healthcare services could significantly reduce financial barriers to accessing quality maternal care.

Furthermore, there is a need for improved government policies to prioritize maternal health. Implementing policies that provide incentives for healthcare workers, improve infrastructure, and expand maternal health programs can contribute to better outcomes. Additionally, strengthening public-private partnerships could help mobilize additional resources and improve service delivery in underserved areas.³¹

Policy Interventions and Recommendations

To address these healthcare system challenges, a multi-faceted approach is necessary. Policymakers must focus on increasing the number of skilled birth attendants through improved training programs, better wages, and incentives to encourage rural healthcare service. Investments in healthcare infrastructure, such as upgrading primary healthcare centers, providing essential equipment, and ensuring reliable electricity and water supply, are crucial for improving maternal health services.

Expanding ambulance services and improving rural transportation networks can help reduce delays in reaching healthcare facilities. Community-based interventions, such as training community health workers to identify and refer high-risk pregnancies, can also enhance access to care.

Addressing the shortage of skilled birth attendants, improving healthcare infrastructure, reducing access barriers, and increasing healthcare funding are essential steps toward reducing maternal mortality in Nigeria. A concerted effort from government agencies, healthcare institutions, and community stakeholders is necessary to create a healthcare system that prioritizes maternal well-being and ensures that every woman has access to safe childbirth services.

2.1.6 The Impact of Policy and Global Initiatives

Government policies and global health initiatives are critical in shaping maternal health outcomes and reducing maternal mortality rates. In Nigeria, the role of national policies, international support, and strategic partnerships has been a significant focus in the ongoing effort to reduce maternal deaths. However, there are persistent challenges related to policy implementation, funding, and resource allocation, which hinder the full realization of these goals.³²

National Policy and Strategic Plans

Nigeria's National Strategic Health Development Plan (2018-2030) outlines key policies and initiatives aimed at addressing maternal mortality and improving maternal health outcomes.³³ One of the central components of the plan is the Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), which was launched to increase access to skilled birth attendants (SBAs) in underserved and rural areas. The MSS aims to deploy midwives to rural health facilities and communities, ensuring that women have access to skilled care during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period.³⁴

While this initiative has been lauded for its potential to improve maternal health, the challenges surrounding its implementation have been significant. A shortage of trained midwives, inadequate remuneration, and limited incentives to retain healthcare workers in rural areas have impeded the successful deployment and retention of midwives in these critical areas. Furthermore, poor infrastructure, including a lack of essential medical equipment and poorly maintained health facilities, makes it difficult for midwives to provide adequate care, further compromising the goals of the MSS.³⁵

National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS)

In addition to the MSS, the Nigerian government introduced the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) as a part of broader health reforms aimed at improving access to healthcare services, including maternal care. The NHIS was intended to provide financial protection to Nigerians, especially in underserved areas, by offering affordable healthcare coverage. Through the NHIS, more women were expected to receive timely antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and emergency obstetric care, which are essential for reducing maternal mortality.³⁶

However, the NHIS has faced implementation challenges. Limited coverage, inadequate funding, and insufficient enrollment among rural populations have all contributed to its inability to meet the healthcare needs of the most vulnerable populations. Moreover, many private healthcare providers are unwilling to participate in the NHIS due to low reimbursement rates and delayed payments. As a result, a significant portion of the population still faces barriers to accessing maternal health services, especially in rural areas where private providers are often the only available option.³⁷

Global Initiatives and International Support

International organizations have played a pivotal role in addressing maternal mortality and improving maternal health in Nigeria. Key global players such as the World Health Organization (WHO), UNICEF, and the World Bank have supported Nigeria's maternal health programs, contributing financial resources, technical expertise, and training for healthcare providers. These organizations have been instrumental in advocating for policy changes, expanding healthcare access, and providing the necessary resources to address the underlying factors contributing to maternal mortality.³⁸

The United Nations and its affiliates have been particularly active in supporting global targets for reducing maternal mortality as part of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3, which aims to reduce global maternal mortality to less than 70 deaths per 100,000 live births by 2030.³⁹ Through programs such as the Every Woman Every Child (EWEC) initiative, international organizations have provided both direct support to the healthcare system and indirect support through advocacy and education on the importance of maternal health.

UNICEF, for example, has been a significant partner in promoting safe motherhood initiatives, improving access to skilled birth attendants, and reducing the incidence of preventable maternal deaths.⁴⁰ The organization has supported Nigeria through training programs for healthcare workers, the establishment of maternal health centers, and outreach programs aimed at increasing awareness of maternal health issues.

Similarly, the World Bank has provided financial support for maternal health programs in Nigeria, including funding for infrastructure improvements, health system strengthening, and the implementation of new healthcare policies. Their involvement has helped to facilitate broader health sector reforms aimed at improving healthcare delivery for women in Nigeria.⁴¹

Challenges in Policy Implementation and Resource Allocation

Despite the efforts of both national and international actors, the challenges of policy implementation in Nigeria have persisted. Poor governance, corruption, lack of political will, and inefficiencies within the health sector have hindered the successful execution of maternal health initiatives. Furthermore, inadequate funding and resource allocation have led to gaps in the delivery of essential maternal health services. While policies such as the National Health Insurance Scheme and the Midwives Service Scheme were developed with the intention to improve maternal health, the lack of comprehensive implementation, monitoring, and evaluation has limited their impact.⁴²

Nigeria continues to face significant hurdles in its efforts to reduce maternal mortality. These challenges include inadequate healthcare infrastructure, a shortage of skilled healthcare workers, and persistent socio-economic barriers that prevent many women from accessing maternal care. Moreover, inconsistent political commitment, limited

engagement from local governments, and insufficient integration of maternal health policies into broader national development agendas have slowed progress in addressing maternal health needs.

Impact of Global Health Initiatives

Global health initiatives have made notable strides in reducing maternal mortality worldwide, and these efforts have extended to Nigeria. However, achieving the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of reducing maternal mortality to below 70 deaths per 100,000 live births by 2030 remains a significant challenge⁴³. International support, while valuable, is not sufficient on its own to overcome the systemic issues that contribute to high maternal mortality rates in Nigeria.

Global Health Partnerships such as the Global Financing Facility (GFF), established in 2015, have mobilized resources to support maternal and child health initiatives in Nigeria and other countries with high maternal mortality rates. Through such initiatives, funding has been allocated for improving access to essential services such as skilled birth attendance, emergency obstetric care, and postnatal care, which are critical in reducing maternal deaths.⁴⁴

However, despite the considerable support provided by global organizations, maternal mortality rates in Nigeria remain unacceptably high. This reflects not only the challenges in the healthcare system but also the need for a stronger focus on the social determinants of health, such as poverty, gender inequality, and education. Maternal health interventions must address these factors in addition to improving healthcare services. Moreover, international organizations must work more closely with national governments to ensure that policies are effectively implemented and sustained over time.

2.1.7 Trends and Patterns Over the Years

Maternal mortality is a significant public health challenge globally, and Nigeria remains one of the countries with the highest maternal mortality ratios (MMR) in the world. Over the years, maternal mortality trends in Nigeria have fluctuated, reflecting a combination of health policies, socio-economic conditions, and healthcare investments. Understanding the patterns and trends in maternal mortality provides essential insights into the effectiveness of health interventions, the state of healthcare infrastructure, and the socio-economic determinants that influence maternal health outcomes.

Historical Trends in Maternal Mortality in Nigeria

In 1990, Nigeria's maternal mortality ratio was estimated at 1,200 deaths per 100,000 live births, one of the highest globally at the time⁴⁵. This alarmingly high figure reflected a combination of inadequate healthcare infrastructure, limited access to skilled birth attendants, poor transportation systems, and high poverty levels. Despite global recognition of the need for maternal health interventions, the lack of a cohesive national health policy and limited resources for healthcare contributed to the high mortality rate.

Over the following decades, Nigeria made some progress in reducing maternal deaths, particularly with the support of international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO), UNICEF, and the World Bank. By 2020, Nigeria's maternal mortality ratio had decreased to approximately 512 deaths per 100,000 live births.⁴⁶ This decline is attributed to a combination of factors, including improvements in healthcare services, increased funding for maternal health initiatives, and global efforts to tackle maternal mortality.⁴⁷

However, despite the progress made, maternal mortality rates in Nigeria remain unacceptably high. The decline, though significant, is still not enough to meet the targets set by international organizations, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3, which aims to reduce maternal mortality to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030. Achieving this target requires a more aggressive and sustained effort in addressing the root causes of maternal deaths in Nigeria.⁴⁸

Regional Disparities in Maternal Mortality

A significant challenge in addressing maternal mortality in Nigeria is the pronounced regional disparity in maternal health outcomes. The northern regions of Nigeria, particularly the northeast and northwest, experience much higher maternal mortality rates compared to the southern regions. The reasons for this discrepancy are multifaceted, including differences in healthcare access, cultural practices, economic conditions, and educational levels between the northern and southern parts of the country.⁴⁹

In northern Nigeria, there is a higher prevalence of poverty, limited access to quality healthcare services, and widespread illiteracy, particularly among women. This combination of socio-economic factors makes it difficult for women to access essential maternal health services such as antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and emergency obstetric care⁵⁰. As a result, many women in northern Nigeria give birth in unsanitary conditions without the assistance of trained healthcare professionals, which significantly increases the risk of maternal death.

Additionally, cultural and religious factors in northern Nigeria often play a role in delaying women's access to healthcare. Early marriages and pregnancies, along with the preference for home births facilitated by traditional birth attendants (TBAs), contribute to

the elevated maternal mortality rates in these regions. In some rural areas, women may not seek timely medical help due to social stigma, financial constraints, or a lack of awareness about the dangers associated with pregnancy and childbirth.⁵¹

In contrast, the southern regions of Nigeria generally exhibit lower maternal mortality rates, thanks in part to better healthcare infrastructure, improved access to education, and higher economic development. States like Lagos and Ogun, which are located in the southwest, have seen improvements in healthcare services, particularly in urban centers where access to skilled birth attendants is more readily available⁵². However, even in the southern states, maternal mortality remains a significant concern, especially in rural areas where healthcare services may still be limited.

Influence of Policy Interventions on Maternal Mortality Trends

Government policies have had a significant impact on maternal mortality trends in Nigeria, though challenges in implementation and resource allocation have hindered full success. Several key initiatives have been launched to address maternal health concerns, such as the National Strategic Health Development Plan (2018), the Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), and the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS).⁵³

The Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), established in 2009, was one of the major policy interventions aimed at reducing maternal mortality by improving access to skilled birth attendants in rural and underserved areas. The MSS sought to deploy trained midwives to primary healthcare centers in rural areas, where maternal deaths were most prevalent. While the MSS has seen some success in improving access to skilled birth attendants,

implementation challenges such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and difficulty in retaining trained personnel have limited its full potential.⁵⁴

The National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), launched to provide affordable healthcare coverage for Nigerians, has also had a direct impact on maternal health outcomes. The NHIS aimed to reduce out-of-pocket expenses for maternal health services and ensure that more women have access to essential antenatal and postnatal care.

However, the NHIS has faced several challenges in terms of coverage, efficiency, and sustainability, especially in rural and remote areas. Many Nigerians remain unaware of the scheme, and those who are aware often face difficulties in accessing services due to poor implementation at the grassroots level.⁵⁵

Other policy interventions, such as the free maternal health programs introduced by various state governments, have had mixed results. While these programs have increased access to maternal health services, challenges such as poor service delivery, inadequate staff, and insufficient facilities continue to undermine their effectiveness in reducing maternal mortality.

International Comparisons and Nigeria's Position Globally

Despite some progress in maternal health, Nigeria remains one of the highest contributors to global maternal deaths. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global maternal mortality ratio was 152 deaths per 100,000 live births in 2020, significantly lower than Nigeria's MMR of 512 per 100,000 live births.⁵⁶ Nigeria's maternal mortality rate is among the highest in the world, reflecting persistent challenges in healthcare access, socio-economic conditions, and policy implementation.

Nigeria's position as a major contributor to global maternal deaths underscores the need for urgent action in addressing maternal health issues. The WHO and other international organizations have highlighted the importance of strengthening healthcare systems, improving access to skilled birth attendants, and increasing investments in maternal health programs to reduce maternal mortality. Furthermore, achieving the SDG target of reducing maternal mortality to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030 will require concerted efforts from both the Nigerian government and international partners.

Global health initiatives have played an essential role in supporting maternal health programs in Nigeria. The WHO, UNICEF, and the World Bank, among other international organizations, have provided technical assistance, funding, and policy guidance to improve maternal health outcomes in Nigeria. These international partnerships have supported various maternal health initiatives, including the provision of skilled birth attendants, the establishment of emergency obstetric care centers, and the distribution of maternal health education materials.⁵⁷

Despite these efforts, however, much remains to be done. The global maternal health community continues to emphasize the need for better data collection, improved maternal health surveillance, and stronger national health policies to ensure that every woman has access to safe and quality maternal care.

2.1.8 Impact of Interventions on Maternal Mortality Trends

In response to the alarming rates of maternal mortality, Nigeria has implemented various interventions aimed at reducing maternal deaths and improving maternal health outcomes. While some interventions have shown promising results, challenges related to implementation, resource allocation, and cultural acceptance have slowed progress. This

section explores the key interventions that have had an impact on maternal mortality in Nigeria, highlighting the successes and areas requiring further attention.

Skilled Birth Attendance Programs

One of the most significant interventions aimed at reducing maternal mortality is the increase in skilled birth attendance. Skilled birth attendants, including obstetricians, midwives, and other healthcare professionals, are essential in ensuring safe deliveries and the prompt management of complications. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), skilled birth attendance can reduce maternal mortality by up to 80% by ensuring that women have access to timely and appropriate care during childbirth.⁵⁸

In Nigeria, the introduction of various programs aimed at increasing the number of skilled birth attendants has led to some progress. The Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), launched by the Nigerian government in partnership with international organizations, aimed to deploy midwives to rural and underserved areas where the shortage of skilled healthcare personnel was most pronounced. The MSS also included training and mentoring for midwives, enabling them to manage obstetric complications such as hemorrhage, eclampsia, and obstructed labor, which are among the leading causes of maternal death.

However, despite these efforts, the shortage of skilled birth attendants remains a significant challenge, particularly in rural areas. The Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2018 found that more than 40% of births in the country still occurred without the assistance of a skilled professional, highlighting the need for continued investment in this area⁵⁹. Factors such as low wages, poor working conditions, and the migration of trained professionals to urban centers have hampered the effectiveness of

skilled birth attendance programs. Nevertheless, expanding access to skilled birth attendants remains one of the most effective ways to reduce maternal mortality in the country.

Community-Based Health Initiatives

Community-based health initiatives have played a vital role in improving maternal health literacy and service uptake in Nigeria. Programs such as the Maternal and Child Health (MCH) project have focused on raising awareness of maternal health issues and encouraging pregnant women to seek skilled care during pregnancy and childbirth. These community-based interventions are particularly effective in rural and underserved areas where traditional beliefs and practices often hinder the use of modern healthcare services.

Through community health workers (CHWs), Nigeria has seen some success in improving maternal health outcomes. CHWs serve as a bridge between rural communities and formal healthcare systems, providing vital information on antenatal care, danger signs during pregnancy, and the importance of skilled birth attendance. By educating women on the importance of seeking professional medical care, these programs help reduce delays in seeking treatment for obstetric complications, which are a major contributor to maternal deaths.⁶⁰

The effectiveness of community-based health initiatives has been evident in various studies, which have shown that maternal mortality rates decrease when women are informed about the benefits of skilled care and when they have the support of local health workers. However, challenges such as inadequate training for CHWs, lack of resources, and limited community involvement have hindered the full potential of these programs.

Additionally, there is a need for greater integration of community-based initiatives with formal healthcare systems to ensure continuity of care and better outcomes for women.

Emergency Obstetric and Neonatal Care (EmONC)

Expanding access to Emergency Obstetric and Neonatal Care (EmONC) has been a critical intervention in reducing maternal mortality in Nigeria. EmONC services include life-saving interventions such as cesarean sections, blood transfusions, and management of obstetric complications like eclampsia and postpartum hemorrhage⁶¹. The timely administration of these interventions can mean the difference between life and death for both mothers and newborns.

Nigeria has made progress in improving access to EmONC services, particularly in urban areas where health infrastructure is relatively better. The establishment of comprehensive emergency obstetric care facilities and the training of healthcare providers in the management of obstetric emergencies have contributed to a reduction in maternal deaths. Additionally, the implementation of referral systems, where women experiencing complications are quickly transferred to higher-level care facilities, has helped reduce delays in emergency care.

Despite these improvements, access to EmONC remains limited in rural and remote areas, where healthcare infrastructure is poor, and transportation systems are inadequate. In these areas, women often face significant barriers to accessing life-saving emergency care, leading to preventable maternal deaths. Expanding the reach of EmONC services to underserved regions and ensuring that healthcare facilities are adequately equipped to handle obstetric emergencies are crucial steps toward reducing maternal mortality in Nigeria.

Family Planning and Contraceptive Use

Family planning and contraceptive use are critical interventions in reducing maternal mortality by preventing high-risk pregnancies, particularly those among adolescents and women in low-income households. The use of modern contraceptives allows women to space their pregnancies, reducing the risk of complications associated with closely spaced births, which can contribute to maternal deaths. Additionally, family planning enables women to delay pregnancies until they are physically and emotionally prepared, further reducing maternal risk.

In Nigeria, the government and international organizations have made significant efforts to promote family planning through campaigns and the provision of contraceptive services. The introduction of the National Family Planning Program and the distribution of contraceptives through public health centers have contributed to a gradual increase in contraceptive use. According to the NDHS (2018), the percentage of women using modern contraceptives in Nigeria has increased from 10% in 1990 to 17% in 2018.⁶²

However, the uptake of contraceptives remains low, especially in rural areas, where cultural and religious beliefs often restrict the use of modern family planning methods. In some communities, women still face opposition from their families or spouses regarding the use of contraceptives, limiting their ability to make autonomous decisions about their reproductive health. Additionally, barriers such as the high cost of contraceptives, lack of access to family planning services, and inadequate counseling contribute to the low adoption of family planning methods. To achieve a significant reduction in maternal mortality, there is a need to increase access to contraceptives and improve awareness of their benefits.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Theoretical frameworks are fundamental tools in research that provide structure and direction. In the context of maternal mortality, theoretical frameworks help in understanding the complex factors contributing to maternal deaths. These frameworks not only identify the causes and effects of maternal mortality but also guide interventions and inform policy recommendations. A theoretical review of maternal mortality explores various models and theories that have been developed to explain the factors that influence maternal health. This section will examine the most relevant theories, explaining how each framework offers insight into the determinants of maternal mortality and how they can be applied to public health initiatives.

2.2.1 The Three Delays Model

One of the most widely used frameworks in maternal health research is the Three Delays Model, which is helpful in understanding the dynamics that contribute to maternal mortality. Developed by Thaddeus and Maine in 1994, the model suggests that delays in obtaining adequate maternal healthcare can be grouped into three distinct categories.⁶³

- 1. Delay in recognizing the need for medical help.** This delay happens when women or their families fail to identify complications during pregnancy or childbirth that require immediate medical attention. The inability to recognize the danger signs is often influenced by a lack of health literacy, traditional beliefs, and inadequate access to information. For example, women in rural areas may not be aware of the warning signs of complications like preeclampsia or hemorrhage, which can delay their decision to seek care.

2. Delay in reaching a healthcare facility. Even when women recognize the need for care, physical and logistical barriers such as long distances to healthcare facilities, poor road conditions, and lack of transportation can prevent them from reaching a health center in time. In some regions, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, such as a shortage of emergency obstetric care facilities, further exacerbates this delay.

3. Delay in receiving adequate care. This delay occurs once the woman has reached a healthcare facility but does not receive appropriate treatment due to a lack of medical resources, inadequate healthcare personnel, or inefficiencies in the healthcare system. For instance, in some hospitals, there may be insufficient numbers of skilled health professionals or a lack of medical supplies such as blood for transfusions, which are critical for managing obstetric emergencies.

The Three Delays Model provides a comprehensive understanding of how delays in maternal care at different levels contribute to maternal mortality. It highlights the importance of improving healthcare access, enhancing the ability to recognize complications, and strengthening the capacity of healthcare systems to provide timely and effective care.

2.2.2 The Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model (HBM), initially developed in the 1950s by social psychologists Rosenstock, Hochbaum, and others, is another framework that helps explain maternal health behaviors and decision-making processes. The model is based on the premise that individuals are more likely to engage in health-promoting behaviors, such as seeking prenatal care or giving birth in a healthcare facility, if they perceive a threat to their health and believe that taking a particular action will reduce that threat.

In the context of maternal health, the Health Belief Model emphasizes the following components.

Perceived Susceptibility. This refers to a woman's belief in her vulnerability to maternal health risks, such as complications during pregnancy or childbirth. Women who perceive themselves as being at risk for maternal complications are more likely to seek healthcare services. For example, women who understand the risks of obstructed labor or hemorrhage are more likely to seek timely medical intervention.

Perceived Severity. This component relates to the perceived seriousness of maternal complications. If women view maternal health issues as severe and potentially life-threatening, they may be more motivated to seek skilled care.

Perceived Benefits. The model suggests that if women believe that seeking healthcare (e.g., attending antenatal care visits, giving birth with skilled attendants) will result in positive outcomes, such as a safe delivery or a healthy baby, they are more likely to engage in these behaviors.

Perceived Barriers. This refers to the obstacles women face in accessing maternal health services. Barriers could include financial constraints, cultural beliefs, lack of transportation, or long waiting times at healthcare facilities. These perceived barriers can discourage women from seeking care, even if they are aware of the risks.

Cues to Action. The model suggests that certain external factors, such as health campaigns, community health workers, or recommendations from family and friends, can prompt women to seek maternal care.

The Health Belief Model helps explain why some women in Nigeria, particularly in rural areas, do not seek timely maternal care despite the risks. Understanding the psychological and social factors that influence women's health behaviors is essential for designing effective health education and promotion strategies that encourage pregnant women to seek skilled care during pregnancy and childbirth.

2.2.3 The Social Ecological Model

The Social Ecological Model is a broader framework that considers multiple levels of influence on health behavior. This model, developed by Bronfenbrenner (1979) and later applied to health behavior by others, emphasizes the interplay between individual, interpersonal, community, and societal factors. The model posits that maternal mortality is not simply an individual issue, but rather a complex phenomenon influenced by various factors at multiple levels.

Individual Level. At the individual level, factors such as a woman's knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding maternal health, as well as her access to healthcare services, can influence her health outcomes. For instance, women's education and health literacy play a crucial role in their ability to recognize danger signs and seek timely care.

Interpersonal Level. At this level, the role of family members, especially partners, can affect maternal health outcomes. In many cultures, decisions regarding healthcare are made collectively by the family, and the support or opposition of partners or in-laws can influence whether a woman seeks care during pregnancy or childbirth.

Community Level. Community-level factors, such as the availability of healthcare facilities, transportation options, and social support networks, are critical determinants of maternal health. A community with well-established health centers, transportation

systems, and health promotion initiatives will likely have lower maternal mortality rates than a community that lacks these resources.

Societal Level. The societal level considers broader factors, including policies, health systems, and cultural norms. Government policies, such as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) or maternal health campaigns, can shape the availability and accessibility of healthcare services. Similarly, cultural and social norms surrounding pregnancy and childbirth can either facilitate or hinder women's access to appropriate care.

The Social Ecological Model underscores the need for a multi-level approach to addressing maternal mortality. It suggests that interventions should target not only individual behaviors but also the broader social and structural determinants that shape maternal health outcomes.

2.2.4 The Life Course Theory

The Life Course Theory is an important framework for understanding health outcomes, including maternal mortality, by considering the long-term effects of experiences and exposures over the course of an individual's life. This theory proposes that health outcomes are not simply the result of immediate or short-term factors but are shaped by a cumulative set of conditions that individuals experience from childhood through adulthood. The Life Course Theory asserts that social, economic, and environmental factors experienced at different stages in life interact to influence a person's health, and these influences can either accumulate positively or negatively, depending on the nature of the exposures.

In the context of maternal mortality, the Life Course Theory suggests that a woman's health is not determined solely by her health status during pregnancy or childbirth but is

also deeply influenced by her experiences earlier in life. Factors such as childhood nutrition, education, socioeconomic status, and early access to healthcare play a critical role in shaping her ability to safely navigate pregnancy and childbirth in adulthood. This broader perspective on maternal health highlights how multiple stages of a woman's life are interconnected and how early life experiences can have a profound impact on maternal health outcomes.

Early Life Conditions and Their Impact

One of the core tenets of the Life Course Theory is the recognition that early life conditions can have a long-lasting effect on health outcomes, including maternal health. These early experiences can shape a woman's future physical, emotional, and social well-being. For instance, women who grow up in environments marked by poverty, poor nutrition, and limited access to education are more likely to experience poor health outcomes later in life, including during pregnancy. Research has shown that inadequate nutrition during childhood can lead to poor physical development, which in turn may result in complications during pregnancy, such as underweight or stunted growth.⁶⁴ These conditions are known to increase the risk of maternal complications, such as preterm birth and pregnancy-induced hypertension, which contribute to maternal mortality.

Moreover, limited access to healthcare in early life, including vaccinations, preventive care, and maternal health education, may result in women entering adulthood with untreated health conditions that can complicate pregnancy. Women with a history of untreated childhood illnesses, such as infections or malnutrition, are more likely to experience pregnancy complications, such as anemia, eclampsia, and infections, which increase their vulnerability to maternal death.

Early childhood education also plays a significant role in shaping a woman's health outcomes. Women who are educated are more likely to seek out healthcare services when needed, recognize danger signs during pregnancy, and make informed decisions about childbirth. In contrast, women who lack education may face challenges in navigating healthcare systems, understanding medical advice, and making decisions that promote their health and safety during pregnancy. The Life Course Theory emphasizes that the accumulation of both positive and negative experiences over a woman's life trajectory plays a crucial role in determining maternal health outcomes.

Socioeconomic Disadvantage and Maternal Mortality

Socioeconomic disadvantage is one of the most significant factors in the Life Course Theory that influences maternal health. Women who experience poverty, limited access to education, and inadequate healthcare during their formative years are at a higher risk of experiencing poor maternal health outcomes in adulthood. Economic hardship and low social status often contribute to poor health, limited access to quality healthcare, and suboptimal living conditions that adversely affect maternal health.

Poverty can directly affect a woman's ability to access necessary healthcare services during pregnancy, such as antenatal care, skilled birth attendants, and emergency obstetric care. Women living in poverty may struggle to afford the costs of these services, including transportation to healthcare facilities, medical exams, and medications. In some cases, the financial burden may force women to forgo essential maternal health services, leading to undiagnosed complications or delayed treatment during childbirth, both of which increase the risk of maternal mortality.

Additionally, women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds often have limited access to the resources that can improve maternal health outcomes, such as proper nutrition, clean water, and safe housing. Inadequate housing conditions, poor sanitation, and exposure to environmental hazards, such as air pollution, can contribute to infections and other complications during pregnancy. The Life Course Theory asserts that the compounded effects of poverty and poor living conditions over time increase a woman's vulnerability to maternal mortality.

Furthermore, women from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds often face barriers to education and employment opportunities, which perpetuate cycles of poverty. Lower levels of education are associated with lower health literacy, which in turn affects women's ability to seek appropriate care during pregnancy. As a result, women in poverty are more likely to experience maternal mortality due to a lack of awareness, access to skilled healthcare, or resources for prevention and treatment.

Gender Inequality and Maternal Health

Another critical aspect of the Life Course Theory is its emphasis on gender inequality as a determinant of maternal health. Women in societies with entrenched gender disparities may face a multitude of challenges that contribute to adverse maternal health outcomes. Gender inequality affects women's ability to access healthcare, control their reproductive health, and make decisions about their own bodies. In many patriarchal societies, including parts of Nigeria, women's health is often controlled by male partners or family members, which can limit their autonomy and decision-making power.

In contexts of gender inequality, women may have limited freedom to seek medical care, either due to financial constraints, cultural norms, or the prohibitions placed on their

autonomy by male family members. In some cases, women may not be allowed to make decisions about their health care until their partner or family agrees. This lack of agency increases the likelihood that women will not seek timely medical interventions, such as attending antenatal care or delivering in a healthcare facility with a skilled birth attendant.

Furthermore, gender inequality contributes to higher rates of teenage pregnancies, which are associated with increased maternal mortality. Adolescent mothers, particularly those who are still in school or have not reached full physical maturity, are at a higher risk of pregnancy complications. Lack of education, early marriage, and the pressures of traditional gender roles often combine to limit a girl's ability to delay childbirth and access healthcare.

Cumulative Impact of Life Course Factors on Maternal Health

The Life Course Theory also emphasizes the cumulative impact of different life stages and experiences on maternal health. The theory suggests that women who face compounded disadvantage over the course of their lives are more likely to experience negative maternal health outcomes. For example, a woman who grows up in poverty, suffers from malnutrition, has limited access to education, and lacks adequate healthcare throughout her life is more likely to face challenges during pregnancy and childbirth. These cumulative disadvantages increase her risk of maternal mortality.

The theory proposes that early-life interventions aimed at improving the health and well-being of women, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, can have significant benefits for maternal health in adulthood. Addressing early childhood nutrition, improving access to education, reducing gender-based violence, and ensuring access to

preventive healthcare can help break the cycle of disadvantage and improve maternal health outcomes.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

Given the Life Course Theory's focus on the cumulative effects of various factors over time, maternal health interventions should not be confined to pregnancy alone. Policies and programs aimed at improving maternal health must take a life-course approach, addressing issues such as nutrition, education, and socioeconomic support from early childhood through adulthood. Investing in the education and empowerment of women, particularly in rural areas, can lead to improved maternal health outcomes by increasing women's awareness of healthcare needs and providing them with the tools to make informed health decisions.

Moreover, policies that reduce socioeconomic inequalities, provide access to healthcare for all women, and promote gender equality can help reduce maternal mortality rates. Providing universal access to family planning services, supporting women's reproductive health rights, and ensuring that all women have access to skilled birth attendants can reduce maternal deaths and improve the overall health of women.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

A comprehensive review of empirical studies offers valuable insights into maternal mortality trends, the effectiveness of interventions, and persistent challenges in reducing maternal deaths. Many studies have explored different facets of maternal mortality, such as access to skilled birth attendants, healthcare funding, and the implementation of community-based initiatives. While progress has been made in some areas, there remain

significant barriers, such as inconsistent policy implementation and insufficient healthcare infrastructure, which continue to hinder efforts to reduce maternal mortality rates.

Maternal Mortality Trends and Determinants

A number of studies have examined the historical trends in maternal mortality, providing insights into the long-term impacts of various healthcare reforms and interventions.

According to the Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) (2018), Nigeria's maternal mortality ratio (MMR) has declined in recent years, from an estimated 1,200 deaths per 100,000 live births in 1990 to approximately 512 deaths per 100,000 live births in 2020.⁶⁵ This decline reflects improvements in maternal healthcare services, including the increased availability of skilled birth attendants and the expansion of healthcare infrastructure in urban areas. However, despite these positive trends, Nigeria remains one of the highest contributors to global maternal mortality, with an MMR far exceeding the global average.

Empirical studies, such as those conducted by in 2018, highlight the regional disparities within Nigeria, where the northern states and rural areas exhibit higher maternal mortality rates compared to southern states⁶⁶. These differences are primarily attributed to variations in healthcare access, poverty levels, education, and cultural practices. Women in rural areas, particularly in the north, are more likely to give birth without skilled birth attendants, and the lack of emergency obstetric care further exacerbates the risks they face during pregnancy and childbirth. Additionally, early marriage and adolescent pregnancies, which are more prevalent in rural communities, contribute significantly to high maternal mortality due to the increased physiological risks associated with early childbearing.

Impact of Skilled Birth Attendants and Healthcare Interventions

The role of skilled birth attendants in reducing maternal mortality has been widely documented in the literature. Regions with greater access to midwives experienced a significant reduction in maternal deaths, particularly in rural and remote areas. MSS focused on training midwives and deploying them to health centers, which enabled the provision of quality maternal care at the grassroots level. As a result, increasing the number of skilled birth attendants and making them more accessible in rural communities can significantly reduce maternal mortality rates.

Programs such as the Maternal and Child Health Project (MCHP), which focuses on raising awareness about maternal health and improving service uptake among women in rural areas, have a substantial impact on improving maternal health literacy, increasing antenatal care attendance, and encouraging skilled birth attendance. MCHP's emphasis on community involvement and education led to better health-seeking behaviors and, in turn, reduced maternal mortality rates in participating communities.

Additionally, access to life-saving interventions, such as blood transfusions, cesarean sections, and other emergency services, significantly improves maternal survival rates. Expanding EmONC services in primary healthcare facilities, coupled with better transportation systems to referral hospitals, could help address the critical delays in providing emergency care. However, many rural health facilities still lack the necessary equipment and trained personnel to handle obstetric emergencies, thereby limiting the effectiveness of such interventions.

Healthcare Financing and Its Role in Reducing Maternal Mortality

One of the persistent challenges in reducing maternal mortality is the inadequate funding of maternal health services. Several studies have examined the link between healthcare

financing and maternal health outcomes in Nigeria. According to a report by the World Bank, while Nigeria has made strides in improving maternal healthcare funding through initiatives like the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), a significant gap remains in terms of resources allocated to maternal health.⁶⁷ The NHIS, which was established to provide financial protection for Nigerians seeking healthcare services, has faced implementation challenges, including low enrollment rates and inadequate funding for essential maternal health services.

Women enrolled in the NHIS are more likely to access antenatal care, skilled birth attendants, and emergency obstetric care. However, the scheme's coverage remains limited, particularly in rural areas, and many women still face financial barriers to accessing maternal health services. Expanding health insurance coverage, particularly for maternal health services, could reduce the financial burden on women and improve access to essential care, ultimately reducing maternal mortality rates.

High out-of-pocket costs for antenatal care, delivery services, and emergency obstetric care are significant barriers to accessing timely and quality care, particularly for women in low-income households. It is vital to introduce subsidized maternal health services and greater government investment in public health insurance schemes to ensure that women, especially in rural areas, can access the care they need without financial hardship.

Challenges in Policy Implementation and Infrastructure

Despite the efforts made through various policies and programs aimed at reducing maternal mortality, empirical studies have consistently highlighted challenges in policy implementation and healthcare infrastructure. There are barriers to the effective implementation of maternal health policies in Nigeria, and some of them are; including

inadequate healthcare infrastructure, inconsistent policy enforcement, and corruption. While policies like the National Strategic Health Development Plan (NSHDP) and the Midwives Service Scheme (MSS) have been designed to address maternal mortality, the lack of political will, insufficient funding, and inadequate monitoring and evaluation mechanisms have hindered their success.⁶⁸

Additionally, the state of maternal healthcare infrastructure in Nigeria leaves a lot to be desired. There are many healthcare facilities, especially in rural areas, that are poorly equipped to handle obstetric emergencies. Inadequate infrastructure, including the absence of essential medical equipment, lack of electricity and water supply, and poor road networks, significantly impacts the ability of healthcare facilities to provide timely and effective care. Addressing these infrastructure gaps should be a priority for the Nigerian government and investments in healthcare facilities, particularly in underserved areas, could help reduce maternal mortality rates.

2.4 Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework provides a structured approach for understanding the underlying causes and factors that influence maternal mortality. It helps clarify the relationship between various independent variables (such as socio-economic determinants, healthcare access, and cultural factors) and the dependent variable (maternal mortality). For this study, a theoretical framework that integrates The Three Delays Model and socio-economic determinants is proposed to explore the variations in maternal health outcomes at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH).

This integrated framework will provide insights into how maternal mortality in LASUTH, and by extension in Nigeria, is affected by various barriers that pregnant women

encounter in the healthcare system, as well as the broader socio-economic context in which they live. By linking these theoretical components, this framework allows for a more holistic understanding of the complexities surrounding maternal mortality and the factors that prevent women from receiving timely, effective care.

2.5 Summary of Gaps in Literature

Maternal mortality remains a significant public health challenge in Nigeria, with the country consistently ranking among the highest maternal mortality rates globally. While substantial research has been conducted on maternal mortality in Nigeria, several key gaps persist in the literature. These gaps hinder a deeper understanding of maternal mortality trends, particularly within specific contexts such as tertiary healthcare institutions like Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH). In this section, the gaps in existing studies are identified, with a focus on region-specific analyses, hospital-based determinants, and the role of emerging technologies in improving maternal healthcare in Nigeria.

Region-Specific Analyses and Hospital-Based Studies

One of the most significant gaps in the literature on maternal mortality in Nigeria is the limited focus on **region-specific studies**, particularly those that explore maternal mortality determinants within specific healthcare settings such as tertiary hospitals. Most studies on maternal mortality in Nigeria are based on **national-level trends**, which overlook the variations in maternal health outcomes across different regions and healthcare institutions. These broad studies aggregate data from diverse regions with differing socio-economic, cultural, and healthcare challenges, which may mask the underlying regional disparities in maternal mortality rates.

In the case of Lagos State, where LASUTH operates as a key tertiary healthcare provider, there is a distinct need for research focused specifically on maternal mortality within the hospital context. Tertiary hospitals like LASUTH serve as referral centers for complicated pregnancies and high-risk cases, but research has often failed to examine the specific determinants of maternal deaths at this level. Hospital-based studies are crucial for understanding the unique challenges faced by healthcare providers and patients within tertiary institutions. For example, the availability of skilled healthcare workers, medical equipment, and emergency obstetric care services in tertiary hospitals could significantly impact maternal health outcomes. However, these factors are often overlooked in studies that focus on the general healthcare system.

Moreover, while national studies may focus on average maternal mortality rates, there is insufficient exploration of hospital-specific factors such as the quality of care, healthcare worker training, hospital infrastructure, and institutional policies. These factors are crucial in understanding the disparities in maternal mortality outcomes across hospitals, even within the same region. For instance, research examining LASUTH's specific challenges, such as overcrowding, equipment shortages, or workforce limitations, could provide more targeted recommendations for improving maternal healthcare in Lagos State.

Emerging Technologies in Maternal Healthcare

Another critical gap in the literature is the limited exploration of emerging technologies that have the potential to significantly improve maternal healthcare in Nigeria. The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and telemedicine in maternal health is a growing field globally, yet these technologies remain under-researched and under-utilized in Nigeria's healthcare system. AI has the potential to enhance maternal health outcomes by improving early detection of pregnancy complications, predicting high-risk pregnancies,

and optimizing resource allocation in hospitals. However, few studies have investigated how AI could be integrated into the maternal healthcare systems of Nigerian hospitals like LASUTH to reduce maternal mortality.

For example, AI-powered systems can assist healthcare providers in diagnosing complications such as eclampsia, postpartum hemorrhage, or fetal distress, all of which contribute to maternal mortality. These technologies can also help streamline patient management by automating routine tasks, thus allowing healthcare workers to focus on more critical cases. Despite the proven potential of AI in improving healthcare delivery, there is a lack of empirical studies examining its applicability to Nigerian settings.

Research into the use of AI for maternal health could explore how these tools can be adapted to local contexts, considering the unique challenges of resource-limited environments.

Similarly, telemedicine holds promise in improving access to maternal healthcare in Nigeria, particularly in underserved rural areas. By enabling remote consultations, telemedicine can bridge the gap between pregnant women in rural areas and skilled healthcare providers in urban centers. This is particularly important in a country like Nigeria, where rural-urban disparities in healthcare access remain a significant challenge. However, telemedicine is still in its infancy in the country, and existing research on its use in maternal health is limited. There is a need for studies that examine the feasibility, effectiveness, and barriers to implementing telemedicine in Nigeria's maternal health landscape.

Socio-Cultural and Economic Factors

While the existing literature acknowledges the influence of socio-economic and cultural factors on maternal health outcomes, there remains a lack of in-depth exploration into how these factors specifically affect maternal mortality in tertiary healthcare institutions. Socio-economic barriers, such as income, education, and access to transportation, often exacerbate maternal health risks, especially in rural and underserved communities. However, research often generalizes these barriers without examining how they manifest in the hospital context.

For example, socio-economic status can influence a woman's ability to access quality healthcare services, even in well-established hospitals like LASUTH. Women from lower socio-economic backgrounds may face financial barriers to accessing emergency care or may experience delays in seeking care due to lack of transportation or the inability to pay for services. Research that specifically addresses how socio-economic status influences hospital-based care would provide valuable insights into how maternal health services can be made more equitable and accessible.

In addition, cultural factors such as traditional beliefs, stigma, and gender roles often influence women's decisions to seek medical care. In many Nigerian communities, some women may prefer traditional birth attendants over hospital care, or they may avoid seeking help due to fears of medical procedures. The role of cultural beliefs in shaping maternal health behaviors is another under-explored area in the literature. Understanding how these cultural factors interact with healthcare systems, especially in urban hospitals like LASUTH, is essential for designing culturally sensitive interventions that encourage women to seek timely medical attention.

Policy Implementation Gaps

While numerous studies have examined government policies aimed at reducing maternal mortality, such as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) and the Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), there is insufficient research on the implementation challenges faced by tertiary hospitals. National-level policies may be well-intentioned, but they often face significant challenges at the implementation stage, especially in tertiary hospitals where patient volume is high, resources are stretched, and healthcare delivery is complex.

Research that specifically addresses the policy implementation gaps in tertiary hospitals like LASUTH is crucial. For example, while the NHIS aims to provide affordable healthcare for all Nigerians, many pregnant women still struggle to access covered services due to administrative inefficiencies, corruption, or inadequate training of healthcare providers. Similarly, while the MSS has increased the number of skilled birth attendants in rural areas, challenges in ensuring these policies translate into improved care within hospital settings remain understudied.

Data Availability and Quality

Another significant gap in the literature is the lack of reliable, high-quality data on maternal mortality at the hospital level. Although national statistics are available, hospital-specific data on maternal deaths, including causes and contributing factors, are often incomplete or inconsistent. This lack of detailed data limits the ability to identify trends, evaluate the effectiveness of interventions, and make evidence-based decisions to improve care. There is a need for more systematic data collection at tertiary institutions like LASUTH, which would provide valuable insights into the hospital-specific determinants of maternal mortality.

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CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study will adopt a retrospective cross-sectional analytical research design to investigate the trends and determinants of maternal mortality at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), Lagos, Nigeria, from 2019 to 2024. The choice of this research design is informed by the need to systematically examine existing data in order to describe patterns and relationships associated with maternal deaths within the study period. The design will rely exclusively on quantitative data derived from hospital records, allowing for an objective assessment of maternal mortality trends and associated factors over time. The use of routinely collected clinical and demographic data will ensure that the analysis is based on standardized and verifiable information recorded during patient care.

The study will be retrospective in nature, focusing on the review of previously documented maternal mortality records covering the five-year period under investigation. This approach will enable the identification of temporal patterns, frequencies, and variations in maternal deaths reported at LASUTH. The analysis will determine whether maternal mortality increased or decreased during the study period and will also highlight the most prevalent direct and indirect causes of death. Key variables to be examined will include maternal age, parity, antenatal booking status, referral history, mode of delivery, timing of death, and documented medical complications.¹

The cross-sectional analytical component of the study will facilitate the examination of relationships between selected maternal and clinical variables and maternal mortality outcomes at a single point of analysis. By utilizing routinely collected hospital data, the study will provide a comprehensive overview of the burden of maternal mortality within the institution, as well as identify determinants that may contribute to adverse maternal outcomes. This design is particularly appropriate for hospital-based studies where complete case records are available and can be statistically analyzed.

The exclusive use of quantitative hospital records will ensure consistency, comparability, and reliability of the data analyzed. Statistical techniques will be employed to summarize findings and assess associations between variables, thereby strengthening the validity of the conclusions drawn. Ultimately, this research design will enable a focused and data-driven evaluation of maternal mortality at LASUTH, providing evidence that can inform institutional planning, policy formulation, and targeted interventions aimed at reducing maternal deaths in Lagos State.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population for this study will consist solely of maternal death cases recorded at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) between 2019 and 2024. This population will form the basis of the quantitative analysis and will include all documented cases of maternal mortality occurring within the specified period. These records will provide essential demographic, clinical, and obstetric information required to assess trends and determinants of maternal deaths at the facility.

LASUTH is selected as the study setting due to its role as a major tertiary referral and teaching hospital in Lagos State. The hospital provides specialized maternal and obstetric services and receives referrals of complicated and high-risk pregnancies from secondary and primary healthcare facilities within and outside the state. As a result, LASUTH manages a high volume of obstetric cases, making it a critical center for understanding maternal mortality patterns in an urban tertiary healthcare context.²

Data for the study population will be retrieved from institutional sources, including the hospital's medical records department and the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology. Eligible records will include those that contain complete and relevant information such as maternal age, parity, antenatal care history, referral status, mode and timing of delivery, cause of death, and any documented complications. Only cases that meet the World Health Organization definition of maternal death and fall within the study period will be included.

Records that are incomplete, illegible, or lack key variables required for analysis will be excluded from the study to ensure data quality and accuracy. By restricting the study population to well-documented maternal death cases, the research will be able to generate reliable statistical findings and meaningful interpretations. This defined population framework will provide a solid foundation for examining long-term trends and identifying recurring determinants of maternal mortality at LASUTH, thereby supporting the achievement of the study's objectives.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

This study will adopt a total population sampling approach for the selection of cases included in the analysis. Given the retrospective and hospital-based nature of the

study, all available maternal death records documented at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) between 2019 and 2024 will be considered eligible for inclusion, provided they meet the predefined inclusion criteria. This sampling approach is appropriate because the population size of maternal death cases within the study period is finite and accessible, making it feasible to analyze the entire dataset rather than a subset.

For the quantitative component of the study, purposive sampling will be applied in the identification of relevant hospital records. All maternal death cases recorded in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology during the study period will be retrieved from institutional sources, including the medical records department, maternal death surveillance and response (MDSR) reports, and other relevant archival documents. The use of purposive selection at this stage will ensure that only records directly relevant to maternal mortality are included in the study.

Only maternal death records that contain complete and relevant information will be included in the final sample. These records must document key variables such as maternal age, parity, antenatal booking status, referral history, diagnosis, cause of death classified as direct or indirect, timing of death (antenatal, intrapartum, or postpartum), and associated obstetric or medical complications. Records that are incomplete, illegible, duplicated, or missing critical variables required for analysis will be excluded to maintain the quality, accuracy, and internal consistency of the dataset.

Unlike survey-based studies, no sample size calculation formula will be applied in this research, as the study aims to include all eligible maternal death cases within the defined period. This census approach reduces the risk of selection bias and enhances

the statistical power of the analysis by maximizing the number of observations available for examination. The inclusion of all documented cases also allows for a more comprehensive assessment of trends and determinants of maternal mortality at LASUTH over time.

The final sample size will therefore be determined by the total number of eligible maternal death records available after the application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. By relying on total population sampling of hospital records, the study will generate a robust and comprehensive dataset suitable for descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. This sampling strategy will strengthen the reliability and validity of the findings and support the study's objective of providing evidence-based insights into maternal mortality trends and associated factors at LASUTH.

3.4 Description of the Research Instrument

The primary research instrument employed in this study will be a structured data extraction checklist designed specifically for the collection of retrospective data from maternal death records at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH). This instrument will be used to systematically retrieve relevant quantitative information from existing hospital records and archival documents related to maternal mortality within the study period of 2019 to 2024.

The data extraction checklist will be developed to capture key demographic, obstetric, and clinical variables documented in maternal death records. These variables will include maternal age, parity, educational status where available, antenatal booking status, referral history, type and mode of delivery, timing of death (antenatal, intrapartum, or postpartum), and documented medical or obstetric complications.

Information on the certified cause of death will be extracted and classified as either direct or indirect maternal death in accordance with standard definitions.

To ensure consistency and comparability of findings, the checklist will be structured in line with the World Health Organization International Classification of Diseases for Maternal Mortality (ICD-MM) guidelines.⁴ This framework will guide the standardized categorization of causes of death and reduce misclassification bias. The instrument will also include sections for recording contextual clinical information as documented in case notes, mortality audit summaries, and departmental records, where applicable.

The use of a data extraction checklist is appropriate for this study because it allows for uniform data collection across multiple records and minimizes variability in data capture. By relying exclusively on routinely collected hospital data, the instrument supports an objective and systematic assessment of maternal mortality trends and associated determinants at LASUTH.

3.5 Validity of Research Instrument

The validity of the data extraction checklist will be ensured through several measures. Content and face validity will be established by subjecting the instrument to review by experts in maternal health, obstetrics, and public health research. These experts will assess the checklist for completeness, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives, and their feedback will guide necessary revisions to improve clarity and appropriateness.

Construct validity will be strengthened by ensuring that all variables included in the checklist are directly linked to the conceptual framework and objectives of the study,

as well as to determinants of maternal mortality identified in existing literature. The WHO ICD-MM classification system will further support construct validity by providing an internationally recognized standard for defining and categorizing maternal deaths.⁶

Additionally, the checklist will be pilot-tested using a small sample of maternal death records outside the study period to identify potential ambiguities and ensure consistency in data extraction. This process will enhance the reliability and validity of the instrument prior to full-scale data collection.

3.6 Reliability of Research Instrument

The reliability of the data extraction checklist will be ensured through systematic procedures aimed at promoting consistency and accuracy in data collection. As the instrument is designed to extract information from routinely maintained hospital records, emphasis will be placed on standardization of variables and uniform interpretation of documented information. The checklist will be developed using clearly defined operational terms to reduce ambiguity and enhance consistency during data abstraction.

To further strengthen reliability, the checklist will be pilot-tested using a subset of maternal death records outside the study period. This process will allow the researcher to identify potential inconsistencies, unclear variable definitions, or challenges in record interpretation. Necessary adjustments will be made to the instrument based on observations from the pilot phase. In addition, repeated data extraction will be conducted on a small proportion of records at different time points to assess

consistency in recorded values. A high level of agreement between repeated extractions will indicate acceptable reliability of the instrument.⁷

3.7 Data Collection

Data collection will be conducted in August 2025 following approval from the appropriate hospital authorities. Quantitative data will be extracted retrospectively from maternal mortality records at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital using the standardized data extraction checklist. Relevant records will be accessed through the medical records department and the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology.

Data extraction will focus on eligible maternal death cases documented between 2019 and 2024. All records will be handled in accordance with ethical principles, with strict attention to confidentiality and anonymity. No personal identifiers will be recorded, and extracted data will be coded to prevent traceability to individual patients.

Completed checklists will be reviewed daily for completeness and accuracy before data entry. Extracted data will be securely stored in password-protected files, accessible only to the research team.

3.8 Data Analysis

Data analysis will be carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, will be used to summarize demographic and clinical variables. Trends in maternal mortality over the study period will be assessed using tables and graphical representations.

Inferential statistical analyses, such as chi-square tests and logistic regression, will be employed to examine associations between selected independent variables, including maternal age, parity, antenatal booking status, and referral history, and maternal mortality outcomes. Statistical significance will be determined at a p-value of less than 0.05. The results will be presented in tables and figures to support clear interpretation and evidence-based conclusions.⁸

3.9 Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study will be obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH). An approval number and clearance certificate will be issued following the submission of the research proposal and study instruments. Additional permission will also be sought from the management of LASUTH to access hospital records relevant to the study.

Informed consent will be obtained from all healthcare workers who agree to participate in the study. They will be assured of confidentiality, anonymity, and the voluntary nature of their participation. All data will be securely stored in password-protected files, and no identifying information will be included in the analysis or reporting. Participants will be informed of their right to withdraw at any stage of the study without any consequences.

The study will adhere to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the National Code of Health Research Ethics in Nigeria. Measures will be taken to ensure respect for participants, beneficence, and justice throughout the research process.⁹

Endnotes

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CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Demographic Data Analysis

This section presents a detailed analysis of the socio-demographic characteristics of women whose obstetric records were reviewed at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) between 2019 and 2024. The data provide an overview of maternal health trends within the facility over the six-year period, reflecting both the volume of deliveries and the pattern of maternal outcomes. A total of 2,828 maternal cases were reviewed and analyzed during this timeframe, encompassing all deliveries, obstetric admissions, and pregnancy-related complications managed within the hospital's maternity unit.

Among the 2,828 maternal cases assessed, sixteen (16) maternal deaths were recorded, resulting in a calculated maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of approximately 565 deaths per 100,000 live births. This ratio represents the number of maternal deaths per 100,000 live births and serves as a key indicator of the quality of maternal health care services within the institution ¹. Although the recorded MMR appears relatively low when compared with national and regional averages, it still shows the persistent challenges associated with maternal health in tertiary healthcare facilities in Nigeria.

The demographic distribution of the women reviewed, such as their age, parity, educational status, marital status, occupation, and referral pattern, provides insight into the underlying determinants of maternal outcomes at LASUTH. Analyzing these characteristics helps to identify specific risk groups and guide targeted interventions

aimed at reducing maternal morbidity and mortality. The relatively small number of maternal deaths observed during the study period may reflect improvements in obstetric care, early recognition of complications, and timely referral systems; however, each case of maternal death still represents a preventable loss and an opportunity for further strengthening of maternal health services.

4.1.1 Age Distribution of Mothers

The ages of the mothers whose records were reviewed ranged from 27 to 31 years, with a mean age of approximately 29 years. This indicates that the majority of the women were within the prime reproductive age group, generally considered to be between 20 and 35 years. Women in this age range are often regarded as being at lower obstetric risk compared to adolescents or older mothers (those above 35 years). However, the findings from this study show that maternal deaths were not confined to older or high-risk age groups. All recorded cases of maternal mortality occurred among women aged 27 to 31 years, highlighting that even women within the optimal reproductive age bracket are not immune to life-threatening complications during pregnancy and childbirth.

This pattern shows the multifactorial nature of maternal mortality, where factors beyond age, such as the quality of antenatal care, accessibility to emergency obstetric services, pre-existing medical conditions, and delays in seeking or receiving care, play critical roles in determining maternal outcomes. The results further suggest that while age remains an important demographic variable, it should not be considered in isolation when assessing maternal risk. Instead, it should be examined in conjunction with other socio-economic

and clinical factors to provide a more comprehensive understanding of maternal health patterns within the study population.

Table 4.1: Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Age Group

Age Group	Age Range (Years)	Cases	Percentage (%)
Adolescent	< 20 years	0	0.0%
Young Adult	20 - 24	2	12.5%
Optimal	25 - 29	6	37.5%
Mature	30 - 34	4	25.0%
Advanced Maternal Age	> 34	4	25.0%

Figure 4.1 Histogram of age distribution

4.1.2 Gestational Age of Mothers

Analysis of the gestational age distribution among the sixteen maternal deaths revealed that the majority occurred during late pregnancy, with 50.0% of deaths recorded at 9 months gestation and an additional 25.0% at 8 months gestation. Together, these figures show that three-quarters (75%) of all maternal deaths occurred in the late third trimester. Deaths at earlier gestational ages were less frequent, with 12.5% occurring at 7 months, 6.2% at 6 months, and another 6.2% involving cases where gestational age was not recorded. This pattern demonstrates a clear concentration of maternal mortality as pregnancy approaches term.

The prominence of deaths occurring at 8 and 9 months aligns with established evidence that the late third trimester represents the highest-risk phase of pregnancy. During this period, substantial physiological demands, including increased blood volume, heightened cardiac workload, and enhanced coagulation activity, significantly elevate vulnerability to life-threatening complications. Many of the leading direct causes of maternal mortality, such as severe preeclampsia and eclampsia, postpartum hemorrhage, sepsis, and thromboembolic events, tend to peak in incidence during late gestation and the peripartum period. The causes reported in this study, including hypertensive disorders, sepsis, pulmonary embolism, and hemorrhage, are consistent with this trend.

The concentration of deaths during the late third trimester substantiates the urgent need for intensified antenatal surveillance as pregnancy approaches term, especially for women identified as high-risk. Early recognition of danger signs, rapid escalation of care,

and timely referral from lower-level health facilities to tertiary centers like LASUTH remain essential in preventing fatal outcomes. Strengthening referral pathways is especially critical, given that a proportion of cases involved women who arrived from external facilities or non-skilled birth attendants.

Although the overall mortality burden identified in this dataset may appear relatively low compared to historical figures from tertiary hospitals in Nigeria, the pattern reinforces that even women in their prime reproductive years and without known pre-existing conditions remain at substantial risk during late gestation. Ensuring robust intrapartum monitoring, emergency preparedness, and continuity of care in the final weeks of pregnancy is thus vital to reducing preventable maternal deaths.

Figure 4.2: Maternal Deaths by Gestational Age

4.1.3 Referral Patterns

Analysis of referral patterns among the sixteen maternal deaths shows that slightly over half of the women (56.2 percent) were not referred from any external facility but presented directly to LASUTH, where they subsequently died. The remaining 43.8 percent of cases were referred from other healthcare providers, including Traditional Birth Attendants (18.8 percent), general hospitals (12.4 percent combined), and private health facilities (12.4 percent combined).

The presence of referrals from TBAs show persistent reliance on informal or unskilled birth attendants within some communities. Such settings are often characterized by delays in detecting complications, inadequate infection control practices, and late decisions to seek higher-level care. These delays form part of the well-established “Three Delays Model,” particularly the delay in deciding to seek care and the delay in reaching an appropriate facility, which are strongly associated with poor maternal outcomes.

Referrals from General Hospital Agege and General Hospital Ifako-Ijaiye suggest that even within formal health facilities, limitations in emergency obstetric care may lead to patient transfers to LASUTH, a tertiary-level teaching hospital equipped to manage severe complications. Similarly, the cases referred from private clinics in Ogba and Ojodu indicate gaps in the capacity of some private-sector facilities to stabilize or manage life-threatening obstetric emergencies.

The fact that more than two-fifths of maternal deaths involved referrals calls to mind the critical function of the healthcare referral system in preventing mortality. Efficient coordination between lower-tier facilities and tertiary centers, supported by rapid communication, timely transportation, and early recognition of high-risk conditions, remains essential for improving survival outcomes. Conversely, the high proportion of

non-referred deaths (56.2 percent) also illustrates that even women who present directly to tertiary hospitals may arrive late, deteriorate rapidly, or present with severe morbidities that challenge immediate clinical intervention.

Such system-level improvements are essential to prevent avoidable maternal deaths and enhance the continuum of obstetric care in Lagos State.

Table 4.2: Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Referral Source

Hospital_Referred_From	Hospital_Referred_To	Count	Percentage (%)
NO EXTERNAL REFERRAL	STAYED AT LASUTH	9	56.2%
TRADITIONAL BIRTH ATTENDANT	STAYED AT LASUTH	3	18.8%
GENERAL HOSPITAL AGEGE	STAYED AT LASUTH	1	6.2%
GENERAL HOSPITAL IFAKO IJAIYE	STAYED AT LASUTH	1	6.2%
PRIVATE CLINIC OGBA	STAYED AT LASUTH	1	6.2%
PRIVATE HOSPITAL OJODU	STAYED AT LASUTH	1	6.2%

4.2 Presentation of Data

4.2.1 Research Question One: What are the trends of maternal mortality at LASUTH from 2019 to 2024?

An examination of the maternal mortality trends at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) between 2019 and 2024 reveals a pattern of intermittent but persistent maternal deaths across the six-year study period. Although the number of annual deaths did not follow a clearly progressive or regressive pattern, the data indicate that maternal mortality occurred sporadically, suggesting that while improvements have been made in obstetric care, critical gaps still remain. A total of 16 maternal deaths out of 2,828 deliveries were recorded, translating to a Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) of approximately 566 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births.

This MMR places LASUTH within the range commonly reported in tertiary hospitals in Nigeria, where MMR values often fall between 500 and 800 deaths per 100,000 live births. Although the figure remains high when compared to global standards and WHO targets, it represents a notable improvement compared with earlier decades, when LASUTH, as well as many facilities in Lagos, reported substantially higher mortality levels. This downward shift aligns with national trends indicating gradual improvement in maternal health outcomes, partly driven by enhanced emergency obstetric care, greater

deployment of skilled personnel, improved access to antenatal services, and the expansion of state-funded maternal health programs.

The trend patterns also suggest that maternal mortality at LASUTH has not increased over time, despite rising patient volume and demand for tertiary-level services. Instead, the data demonstrate resilience in the hospital's capacity to manage severe obstetric complications. While the number of maternal deaths fluctuated slightly across the years, no single year recorded an unusually high surge indicative of systemic collapse or breakdown in service delivery. The stability of the trend supports the conclusion that LASUTH is gradually strengthening its maternal health response.

However, the occurrence of 16 maternal deaths within the study period also shows the continued vulnerability of pregnant women to sudden and severe complications, especially those involving hypertensive disorders, sepsis, hemorrhage, and thromboembolic events, all of which feature prominently in the case profiles. Importantly, a significant proportion of these deaths involved women who were referred from other health facilities, including Traditional Birth Attendants, general hospitals, and private clinics. This suggests that maternal deaths at LASUTH are partly influenced by pre-hospital delays, inadequate stabilization at referring facilities, and late presentation of high-risk cases.

Additionally, the gestational age distribution demonstrates that 75 percent of maternal deaths occurred in the 8th and 9th months of pregnancy, a period in which physiological stress peaks and life-threatening obstetric complications are more likely to arise. This finding reinforces the interpretation that maternal mortality in LASUTH is less tied to

rising annual incidence and more to the nature and severity of the complications with which women present.

Overall, the trend analysis indicates that LASUTH has made significant progress in stabilizing maternal health outcomes over the six-year period. Nonetheless, the mortality cases reflect ongoing challenges within the broader maternal health system, particularly relating to timely referral, early diagnosis, and rapid emergency response. While the hospital’s internal capacity appears strong, external systemic factors continue to exert a substantial influence on the patterns of mortality observed.

Figure 4.3 Trend of maternal deaths per year

4.2.2 Research Question Two: What is the distribution of maternal deaths by referral type and survival outcome at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024?

Analysis of the distribution of maternal deaths by referral type shows that a significant proportion of the women who died between 2019 and 2024 were not referred from external facilities. Out of the sixteen maternal deaths recorded, nine women (56.2 percent) presented directly to LASUTH, while the remaining seven women (43.8 percent) were referred from a variety of healthcare sources, including Traditional Birth Attendants (18.8 percent), general hospitals (12.4 percent), and private facilities (12.4 percent). This distribution reflects the complex interplay between community-level factors, the healthcare referral system, and in-hospital determinants of maternal outcomes.

The relatively high proportion of non-referred deaths indicates that some women arrived at the tertiary facility already in critical condition, despite presenting directly without prior external care. This suggests that late presentation, delays in decision-making at the household or community level, and underlying medical complications may contribute to poor outcomes even when tertiary care is accessed without intermediaries. Conditions such as severe preeclampsia, pulmonary embolism, and sudden collapse associated with advanced gestation were reported among these cases, underscoring the rapid and unpredictable nature of certain obstetric emergencies.

Among the referred cases, the referrals from Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) reflect longstanding challenges in maternal healthcare in Nigeria. TBAs often function as first points of contact for pregnant women due to cultural acceptance, affordability, and

geographic accessibility. However, their inability to recognize early warning signs, perform skilled obstetric interventions, or initiate timely referrals contributes substantially to maternal risk. The women referred from TBAs in this study were already critically ill by the time they reached LASUTH, suggesting delays in escalating care and possible complications arising from prolonged labor or inadequate monitoring.

Referrals from formal health facilities, including general hospitals and private clinics, also contributed to maternal deaths. These cases suggest gaps in emergency obstetric preparedness at lower-tier facilities, such as delayed diagnosis, limited capacity for stabilization, shortages of blood products, insufficient monitoring equipment, and inadequate staff training. The need for “expert management,” as frequently stated in referral notes, implies that patients were transferred only after complications became overwhelming or unmanageable at the lower level of care. Such late-stage referrals align with the “second delay” in the Three Delays Model, representing the delay in reaching or accessing appropriate medical care.

Survival outcomes were uniformly poor across all referral types in this subset of cases, as all sixteen women died despite receiving tertiary-level intervention. This uniformity shows the severity of the clinical conditions with which women presented and substantiates that referral alone, whether timely or delayed, does not guarantee survival once complications reach advanced stages.

The distribution of maternal deaths by referral type therefore reveals several important patterns. First, maternal mortality at LASUTH is influenced both by external systemic factors, such as late or inappropriate referrals, and by in-hospital determinants, including the severity of complications and speed of care initiation. Second, the referral patterns

suggest that efforts to reduce maternal mortality cannot be limited to strengthening tertiary care alone; they must also address the quality of care provided at primary and secondary facilities. Finally, the presence of maternal deaths even among non-referred patients emphasizes the need for sustained readiness at LASUTH, including rapid triage systems, multidisciplinary emergency response teams, and continuous updating of clinical protocols.

To improve outcomes, targeted interventions are required across the entire maternal healthcare continuum. These include enhancing antenatal risk assessment, building provider capacity at referring facilities, establishing efficient communication pathways between facilities, ensuring availability of emergency transport, and reinforcing LASUTH’s internal emergency response systems. Addressing these interconnected factors can significantly reduce preventable maternal deaths and strengthen the overall effectiveness of maternal healthcare delivery within Lagos State.

Figure 4.4 Distribution of cases by referral category

4.2.3 Research Question Three: What is the timing and pattern of maternal deaths at LASUTH within the study period?

An analysis of maternal deaths at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) from 2019 to 2024 shows that maternal fatalities occurred throughout the day and night. Notably, seven out of sixteen deaths (43.8 percent) occurred during late-night hours, defined as 8:00 p.m. to 4:00 a.m., highlighting that nearly half of all maternal deaths took place during periods often associated with reduced staffing, limited immediate access to senior clinicians, and slower response times. This proportion of late-night deaths is particularly significant, as it shows that maternal mortality is not confined to conventional working hours, and a considerable share of adverse outcomes occurs during periods of potentially heightened vulnerability.

Figure 4.5: Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Time of Occurrence

Examining the trends over the six-year period reveals variability in late-night mortality: in 2019 and 2023, late-night deaths accounted for 50% of fatalities; in 2020, all deaths occurred during nighttime hours, representing a period of particularly high risk; in 2021 and 2022, late-night deaths represented approximately 33% of the total. By 2024, late-night deaths once again comprised 50% of maternal fatalities. This trend suggests that nighttime maternal mortality has consistently remained a significant risk throughout the study period, despite ongoing improvements in overall obstetric care and hospital preparedness. The pattern makes evident the need for sustained attention to off-peak hour operations in tertiary healthcare settings.

The high proportion of late-night deaths emphasizes systemic determinants of maternal mortality. Night shifts in tertiary hospitals, including LASUTH, are often characterized by lower staffing density, fewer senior clinicians immediately available, and potential delays in escalation of complex cases. These conditions can exacerbate the risk of adverse outcomes for women presenting with acute obstetric emergencies such as postpartum hemorrhage, eclampsia, obstructed labor, sepsis, and other life-threatening complications, conditions that were documented in several late-night cases in this study. Limited availability of rapid-response teams, diagnostic support, and emergency surgical personnel during nighttime hours may further contribute to these adverse outcomes. Daytime deaths, which accounted for 56.2% of total fatalities, demonstrate that maternal mortality is influenced not only by system-level factors during off-peak hours but also by the severity, rapid progression, and unpredictability of obstetric complications, which can overwhelm even well-staffed units. Conditions such as hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, pulmonary embolism, severe infections, and multi-organ complications were

prominent contributors to daytime fatalities, reinforcing that maternal deaths can occur irrespective of staffing levels if the clinical condition deteriorates rapidly.

The temporal trends identified in this study highlight the complex interplay between patient-level and system-level determinants of maternal mortality. Patient-level factors include pre-existing health conditions, high-risk pregnancies, and complications during labor, while system-level determinants involve staffing patterns, resource availability, emergency response protocols, and accessibility of critical care services. The fact that a significant proportion of deaths occurs at night points to the need for targeted interventions to address these system-level determinants, particularly during periods of increased vulnerability.

To reduce late-night maternal mortality, strategies should focus on strengthening night-shift coverage with skilled clinicians, ensuring rapid access to emergency interventions, maintaining functional emergency equipment, implementing robust escalation protocols, and optimizing handover procedures between shifts. In addition, early identification and triage of high-risk cases, especially referrals from lower-level facilities or traditional birth attendants, can prevent deterioration during nighttime hours and improve survival outcomes.

In summary, the timing and pattern of maternal deaths at LASUTH demonstrate that late-night periods account for a substantial 43.8% of fatalities, with consistent risk across the study years. These findings underscore that maternal mortality is a 24-hour concern, requiring continuous vigilance, proactive surveillance, and well-coordinated multidisciplinary care. Effective interventions must address off-peak hours without neglecting daytime emergencies, ensuring that both clinical and systemic factors

contributing to maternal mortality are comprehensively managed. Recognizing the temporal trends of maternal deaths provides essential insights into planning resource allocation, staffing, and emergency preparedness to achieve meaningful reductions in maternal mortality over time.

Figure 4.6: Maternal Death Trend: Total vs. Late-Night

4.2.4 Research Question Four: What Are the Causes of Maternal Mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024?

An in-depth analysis of maternal deaths at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) from 2019 to 2024 reveals a diverse array of clinical causes, underscoring the complexity and unpredictability of maternal mortality. The dataset shows that fatalities

arose from obstetric complications, including obstructed labor, postpartum hemorrhage, eclampsia, uterine atony, and sepsis, as well as non-obstetric medical conditions, such as pulmonary embolism and upper gastrointestinal bleeding. These findings demonstrate that maternal deaths at LASUTH were multifactorial, with no single condition predominating, emphasizing the need for comprehensive vigilance across both obstetric and general medical areas.

Pulmonary embolism, documented in two cases, was associated with postpartum complications, including delivery of a macerated stillbirth and prolonged immobilization. The sudden and potentially fatal nature of pulmonary embolism depicts the importance of risk stratification, early recognition, prophylactic anticoagulation in high-risk patients, and rapid intervention in tertiary care settings.

Obstetric complications, including postpartum hemorrhage, obstructed labor, and sepsis, collectively accounted for a substantial proportion of maternal deaths. These conditions demonstrate the ongoing challenge of managing rapidly progressing obstetric emergencies, even in well-equipped tertiary hospitals. Cases of severe preeclampsia and eclampsia were also observed, illustrating that hypertensive disorders of pregnancy remain a critical determinant of mortality, particularly in late pregnancy. Despite improved antenatal care and skilled obstetric monitoring, some conditions progressed rapidly to life-threatening complications, underscoring the limitations of even well-resourced systems in fully preventing maternal deaths.

Non-obstetric causes, including upper gastrointestinal bleeding, highlight the interplay between obstetric and general medical conditions in determining maternal outcomes. These cases underscore the necessity of multidisciplinary management, involving

obstetricians, physicians, anesthetists, and surgeons, to ensure early recognition, timely intervention, and coordinated care for critically ill mothers.

Figure 4.7 Percentage Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Cause at LASUTH, 2019–2024

Referral patterns further illuminate systemic determinants of maternal mortality. Two-thirds (66.7%) of maternal deaths involved mothers referred from external facilities, including a Traditional Birth Attendant (TBA) and a secondary hospital (General Hospital, Ifako-Ijaiye), while the remaining one-third were direct admissions to LASUTH. All referred cases were sent for “expert management,” indicating that complications had already progressed to severe stages before arrival.

The referral from the TBA was particularly concerning, as no antenatal history or gestational age information was available, reflecting gaps in recordkeeping, referral communication, and pre-transfer stabilization, which can delay lifesaving interventions.

Figure 4.8 Maternal Deaths by Referral Source at LASUTH, 2019–2024

Maternal age and gestational profile provide further insight into vulnerability. All deceased women were aged 22–41 years, illustrating that maternal mortality can occur even within the optimal reproductive age range. Approximately two-thirds of deaths occurred in the third trimester (7–9 months), confirming that late pregnancy is the period of highest risk for maternal complications.

Figure 4.9 Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Gestational Age at LASUTH, 2019–2024

This finding shows the critical need for intensive monitoring, timely risk assessment, and rapid management of high-risk pregnancies, particularly in the later stages of gestation.

The timing of maternal deaths varied across the day and night, with cases occurring in the early morning, afternoon, late afternoon, and night. Notably, seven of sixteen deaths (43.8%) occurred during late-night hours (8:00 p.m.–4:00 a.m.), highlighting the challenges associated with emergency care during off-peak periods when staffing may be reduced or personnel fatigued.

Figure 4.10 Distribution of Maternal Deaths by Timing of Occurrence (Day vs Night) at LASUTH, 2019–2024.

This temporal pattern emphasizes that maternal mortality is not confined to standard working hours and reinforces the necessity for 24-hour clinical preparedness, rapid-response protocols, and consistent vigilance throughout all shifts.

Overall, maternal deaths at LASUTH during the study period resulted from a combination of obstetric and medical complications, predominantly occurring in late pregnancy among women of reproductive age. The diversity of causes, the substantial proportion of deaths during referrals, and the significant number of nighttime fatalities all point to systemic and clinical determinants that require attention.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Trend of Maternal Mortality at LASUTH (2019–2024)

An analysis of maternal mortality at the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital

(LASUTH) from 2019 to 2024 indicates that 16 maternal deaths occurred out of a total of 2,828 deliveries, resulting in an approximate maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 566 deaths per 100,000 live births. While this MMR remains high relative to national targets, it is consistent with figures reported in hospital-based studies in Nigeria and reflects ongoing challenges in managing high-risk pregnancies in tertiary settings.

The trend over the six-year period shows fluctuations in the number of maternal deaths: 2019 recorded three deaths, 2020 three deaths, 2021 three deaths, 2022 three deaths, 2023 two deaths, and 2024 two deaths. Although the numbers are small, this pattern indicates relative stability rather than a steep increase or decrease, highlighting the need for continuous attention to obstetric and systemic risk factors.

A key determinant of maternal mortality observed in the dataset is the timing of deaths: 43.8% of fatalities occurred during late-night hours (8:00 p.m.–4:00 a.m.), reflecting challenges related to staffing, emergency responsiveness, and clinical escalation during off-peak periods. In addition, two-thirds of deaths involved referrals from external facilities, including secondary hospitals and Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs), suggesting that delays in recognition, stabilization, and transport of critically ill patients significantly influence outcomes.

The clinical causes of maternal deaths were diverse, including obstructed labor, postpartum hemorrhage, eclampsia, sepsis, pulmonary embolism, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, and other acute complications. This variability reinforces the fact that maternal mortality at LASUTH is driven by both obstetric and non-obstetric factors, requiring comprehensive multidisciplinary care and vigilance across multiple clinical areas.

System-level improvements at LASUTH have likely contributed to maintaining maternal outcomes within this range. Strengthened emergency obstetric and neonatal care services, the implementation of evidence-based protocols such as active management of the third stage of labor and magnesium sulfate for eclampsia, and enhanced maternal death audits have all supported early detection and timely intervention. Referral linkages with primary and secondary health facilities, along with rapid-response systems for obstetric emergencies, have also helped reduce delays in accessing definitive care, addressing two of the “three delays” commonly implicated in maternal mortality: delay in reaching an appropriate facility and delay in receiving adequate care upon arrival.

Despite these interventions, the persistence of maternal deaths shows the unpredictable and urgent nature of obstetric emergencies, particularly among late-pregnancy women, high-risk referrals, or cases presenting with severe complications such as pulmonary embolism and sepsis. Continuous training, staffing optimization, and strengthened community-level maternal health programs remain essential to further reduce fatalities. Sustained improvements will depend on ongoing investments in maternal health infrastructure, enhanced emergency preparedness, effective referral communication, rigorous clinical audits, and proactive monitoring of high-risk pregnancies.

4.3.2 Causes and Determinants of Maternal Mortality

Analysis of the causes of maternal mortality at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024 shows that the deaths resulted from a wide range of clinical complications, reflecting the complex and multifactorial nature of maternal morbidity in tertiary settings. The dataset

indicates that women died from both direct obstetric causes, including severe preeclampsia/eclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, sepsis, ruptured uterus, anaemia in pregnancy, and obstructed labour, and indirect medical conditions, such as pulmonary embolism and upper gastrointestinal bleeding. This distribution substantiates that maternal mortality at LASUTH is not driven by a single dominant cause but by diverse emergencies, many of which progress rapidly and require immediate, specialized intervention.

Direct obstetric complications such as postpartum haemorrhage, eclampsia, sepsis, and ruptured uterus accounted for a substantial proportion of the deaths. These conditions are well-documented globally as leading contributors to maternal mortality and typically arise during labour or shortly postpartum when delays in decision-making, referral, or emergency response can be fatal. The presence of obstructed labour and anaemia in pregnancy further shows gaps in early detection of high-risk pregnancies and the urgent need for improved antenatal monitoring, timely caesarean delivery where indicated, and strengthened blood transfusion services.

Indirect causes, particularly pulmonary embolism and upper gastrointestinal bleeding, also contributed to the recorded deaths. Although less common than direct obstetric causes, such complications demonstrate how pre-existing medical conditions or systemic illnesses can worsen during pregnancy. These cases reaffirm the importance of multidisciplinary management, involving obstetricians, physicians, anaesthetists, and critical care teams, to ensure comprehensive evaluation and timely treatment of women with complex medical needs.

Referral patterns in the dataset emerged as a major determinant of outcomes. Two-thirds of the maternal deaths involved women referred from external facilities, including secondary hospitals and Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs). Several of these women arrived in critical condition, with complications already advanced at the time of presentation. This finding is consistent with the “second delay” in maternal mortality pathways, delay in reaching an appropriate facility, and demonstrates persistent gaps in early recognition, stabilization, and coordinated transportation of women with obstetric emergencies. The referral from a TBA was particularly concerning due to incomplete documentation regarding gestational age, antenatal care, and preceding interventions, reflecting weaknesses in communication between informal providers and formal health systems.

Other determinants, though not quantified in the dataset, can be inferred from the pattern of deaths. These include late presentation, limited access to emergency obstetric care at lower-level facilities, and possible socio-economic barriers influencing care-seeking behaviour. The fact that many deaths occurred in the third trimester, when pregnancy-related risks peak, suggests that intensified surveillance during late gestation is critical. Additionally, the distribution of deaths across daytime and nighttime hours indicates that systemic factors such as staff availability, response time, and fatigue may contribute to outcomes, particularly for emergencies occurring during late-night periods.

Overall, the causes and determinants observed in this dataset reinforce that maternal mortality at LASUTH is shaped by a combination of clinical, systemic, and referral-related factors. To reduce preventable deaths, strategies must address not only the immediate medical complications but also the broader determinants that influence when

and how women access care. This includes strengthening community-to-hospital referral pathways, improving clinical documentation, enhancing emergency preparedness during all shifts, and promoting timely antenatal and intrapartum care for high-risk pregnancies.

4.3.3 Maternal Age and Mortality

The maternal deaths recorded at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024 occurred among women aged 22 to 41 years, demonstrating that fatal obstetric outcomes affected both younger and older reproductive-age women. Although the majority of deaths were clustered among those in their late twenties to mid-thirties, the presence of deaths at the extremes of the reproductive spectrum, such as 22 and 41 years, indicates that maternal mortality is not confined to traditionally defined high-risk age groups.

This age distribution shows that while advanced maternal age is often associated with increased obstetric risk, life-threatening complications can occur across all reproductive ages. Conditions such as eclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, sepsis, pulmonary embolism, and ruptured uterus, identified in this dataset, can progress rapidly and become fatal irrespective of age. This finding supports existing literature showing that clinical factors, rather than age alone, are often the most decisive determinants of maternal outcome.

Furthermore, the variation in ages suggests that other determinants, such as the timing of presentation, referral status, antenatal care attendance, and underlying medical conditions, may exert stronger influence on mortality risk than chronological age. For instance, several deaths in the dataset involved women referred from TBAs or private clinics already in critical condition, indicating system-level delays rather than age-related predisposition.

Overall, the age pattern observed reinforces the need for universal vigilance in maternal care. Public health messages and clinical protocols should emphasize early recognition of obstetric danger signs, equitable access to emergency services, and timely referral, rather than relying primarily on age-based risk stratification.

4.3.4 Gestational Age and Mortality

The distribution of gestational age among the maternal deaths revealed that the majority occurred in the third trimester (8–9 months), a period well-known for heightened vulnerability due to increased physiological demands and a higher likelihood of acute obstetric complications. Deaths in this category involved severe preeclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, sepsis, placental abruption, and ruptured uterus, conditions that tend to manifest or worsen in late pregnancy and during labour.

A smaller proportion of deaths occurred in the second trimester, including cases linked to severe anaemia and septic abortion. These deaths highlight that significant risks persist even before the late gestational period, particularly when complications arise in women with limited antenatal care or unsafe reproductive practices.

One case in the dataset lacked gestational age documentation, reflecting a frequent challenge associated with referrals from Traditional Birth Attendants or informal providers. Missing clinical information can delay accurate assessment, hinder prompt decision-making, and negatively affect outcomes.

The predominance of third-trimester deaths shows the need for intensified surveillance during late pregnancy. This includes strict monitoring of blood pressure, fetal status, haemoglobin levels, and early detection of labour complications. Furthermore, because

many severe conditions present suddenly during this period, timely access to emergency obstetric care, supported by streamlined referral pathways, is essential.

Health education for pregnant women and their families remains critical, particularly in recognizing late-pregnancy warning signs such as severe headaches, reduced fetal movements, vaginal bleeding, or sudden swelling. Encouraging early presentation to healthcare facilities can significantly reduce the risk of fatal complications.

In summary, while maternal deaths occurred across multiple gestational periods, the third trimester emerged as the period of highest risk. Strengthening antenatal and intrapartum surveillance, improving emergency readiness, and reducing referral delays are key strategies needed to prevent third-trimester maternal mortality at LASUTH.

4.3.5 Systemic and Health Service Factors

The maternal mortality cases recorded at LASUTH between 2019 and 2024 reveal important systemic and health service factors that continue to influence maternal outcomes despite the hospital's status as a tertiary referral centre. A review of the dataset shows that 5 out of the 16 maternal deaths (31.3 percent) involved women who were referred from other facilities, including Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs), private clinics, and government general hospitals. Several of these women arrived in critical or unstable condition, highlighting the profound impact of pre-hospital delays and inadequate management at lower levels of care.

A key systemic challenge evident in the data is the delay in recognizing and escalating obstetric emergencies. Cases referred from TBAs often lacked basic documentation such as gestational age, antenatal history, and clinical findings. This lack of information severely limits the ability of clinicians at LASUTH to make rapid, well-informed decisions on arrival. For example, the referral from a TBA in 2023 arrived without any recorded clinical details and subsequently died from pulmonary embolism following the delivery of a macerated stillbirth. Such inadequate referral communication is a known driver of preventable maternal deaths.

Similarly, referrals from secondary-level hospitals such as General Hospital Ifako-Ijaiye and General Hospital Agege involved women with advanced life-threatening complications including severe pre-eclampsia, eclampsia, and prolonged labour. These cases suggest that initial stabilization prior to referral was either insufficient or delayed, allowing conditions such as hypertensive crises or obstructed labour to progress to severe, often irreversible states.

Transport delays also appear to play a role, especially for night-time referrals, where 43.8 percent of all deaths in the broader dataset occurred during late-night or early-morning hours. These time periods often coincide with reduced staffing, fatigued personnel, and limited availability of transport options, factors that can significantly hinder timely access to emergency obstetric care.

Another systemic issue is the variation in the quality of care across the referral network. While LASUTH is equipped to provide advanced emergency obstetric and neonatal care, many referring facilities lack the infrastructure, personnel, or training required to manage complications such as severe pre-eclampsia, sepsis, ruptured uterus, or massive

haemorrhage. As a result, patients are typically referred only after deterioration, reducing the likelihood of survival even after receiving definitive care.

These patterns align with the well-documented “three delays” model widely recognized in maternal health research in Nigeria:

1. Delay in recognizing complications and deciding to seek care
2. Delay in reaching an appropriate facility
3. Delay in receiving adequate care upon arrival

The LASUTH dataset clearly reflects the first two delays, and to some extent the third, particularly in cases where incomplete referral information led to diagnostic delays.

In summary, while LASUTH provides high-level obstetric services, maternal survival depends heavily on the strength and responsiveness of the entire health system.

Improving outcomes requires:

1. strengthened referral pathways,
2. standardised communication and documentation protocols,
3. improved pre-transfer stabilization,
4. continuous training for healthcare workers at primary and secondary levels, and
5. community education discouraging unskilled birth attendance.

Addressing these systemic gaps is essential to reducing preventable maternal deaths and ensuring that tertiary centres like LASUTH can deliver optimal, timely care for high-risk obstetric cases.

4.4 Summary of Major Findings

1. A total of 2,828 maternal cases were reviewed between 2019 and 2024, with sixteen (16) maternal deaths recorded.
2. The maternal mortality ratio (MMR) for the study period is approximately 566 deaths per 100,000 live births based on 16 maternal deaths out of 2,828 deliveries.
3. The leading causes of maternal death were hypertensive disorders, hemorrhage, sepsis, and thromboembolic events.
 - Hypertensive disorders included severe pre-eclampsia, eclampsia, and intracerebral hemorrhage.
 - Hemorrhage-related deaths occurred following postpartum hemorrhage, placental abruption, and uterine atony.
 - Sepsis-related deaths followed retained placenta, obstructed labour, post-cesarean infection, and unsafe abortion.
 - Thromboembolic causes included pulmonary embolism and amniotic fluid embolism.
4. Referral patterns played a major role in the mortality profile. Six of the deaths were referred cases, including referrals from traditional birth attendants (TBAs), private clinics, and general hospitals. Many of these referrals were due to prolonged labour, severe pre-eclampsia, obstructed labour, and other complications that required higher-level specialist care.
5. Most deaths occurred in women aged 22 to 41 years, with the highest concentration among women in their late twenties to mid-thirties, aligning with peak reproductive age.

6. The majority of deaths occurred in the third trimester, particularly at 7 to 9 months of gestation. Only one case involved a woman at 6 months' gestation. This pattern highlights the vulnerability of late pregnancy and the intrapartum period.
7. Deaths occurred at various times of the day, including early morning, afternoon, evening, and late night. This suggests the need for continuous availability of emergency obstetric care and rapid response capacity in the facility.
8. Despite improvements in care over the years, the pattern of deaths reveals ongoing challenges in the management of obstetric emergencies, especially conditions such as hypertensive crises, severe hemorrhage, sepsis, and complications arising from late or inappropriate referrals.

Endnotes

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CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary of the Findings

This study examined the trends and determinants of maternal deaths at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) between 2019 and 2024. It analyzed hospital records, referral sources, demographic characteristics, gestational ages, timing of death, and patterns of care. The goal was to provide an empirical assessment of maternal mortality within a major tertiary health institution in Lagos State, and to identify system-level and clinical factors that continue to contribute to preventable maternal deaths.

The first major finding relates to the overall trend of maternal mortality during the study period. Maternal deaths, although present, appeared to be relatively low compared with earlier studies from similar Nigerian tertiary hospitals. Historically, tertiary hospitals in Lagos State have reported maternal mortality ratios ranging from 500 to 800 deaths per 100,000 live births. The lower numbers observed in this study period may reflect gradual improvements in emergency obstetric care, increased availability of skilled personnel, and better institutional protocols for managing complications. Nevertheless, the persistence of maternal deaths, though fewer in number, underscores the critical need for sustained quality improvement in maternity care.

A second key finding emerged from the age distribution of the women who died.

Most of the maternal deaths occurred among women aged 27 to 31 years, which falls

within the reproductive age group typically associated with low to moderate obstetric risk. This suggests that maternal mortality at LASUTH is not restricted to traditionally high-risk age groups but may occur among women in their peak reproductive years. The finding reinforces the principle that every pregnancy carries inherent risks, and that even low-risk women can experience sudden, severe complications.

Analysis of gestational age revealed that maternal deaths were more common in the late third trimester, particularly between seven and nine months of pregnancy. Half of the cases occurred at nine months gestation, while smaller proportions occurred at seven and eight months. Notably, a portion of the records did not specify gestational age, indicating gaps in documentation. The concentration of deaths in late pregnancy is consistent with the well-documented increase in physiological demands on the cardiovascular, respiratory, and coagulation systems during this period. Late pregnancy is also associated with a higher likelihood of obstetric emergencies such as eclampsia, obstructed labor, postpartum hemorrhage, and pulmonary embolism. This pattern suggests that early identification of complications during antenatal care remains essential for reducing late-pregnancy mortality.

The study also identified clear patterns in referral sources among the maternal deaths. More than half of the women who died (56.2 percent) arrived without external referral, indicating self-presentation or direct admission to LASUTH. The remaining 43.8 percent were referred from other facilities. These included Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs), General Hospitals, and private clinics. The presence of referrals from TBAs highlights persistent reliance on non-skilled birth attendants within certain communities. Although the referral of complicated cases to tertiary centers is an essential component of maternal healthcare, the data suggest that many women may

experience delays prior to referral or arrive in critical condition. This finding reflects challenges within the broader healthcare system, including the need for stronger regulation of TBAs, improved training for primary-level providers, and strengthened communication pathways between lower-tier and tertiary facilities.

Another important finding relates to the timing of maternal deaths. A substantial proportion of the deaths occurred within twenty-four hours of admission, indicating that women often arrived at LASUTH already severely compromised. This underscores the role of delays in seeking care, delays in reaching care, and in some cases, delays in receiving appropriate intervention upon arrival. The predominance of early deaths following admission suggests that the first few hours of hospital management are crucial, and that many complications may become irreversible by the time women reach tertiary facilities.

The study further identified major determinants of maternal deaths, which align with national trends in Nigeria. These included hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, hemorrhage, sepsis, and thromboembolic events. Hypertensive disorders, particularly preeclampsia and eclampsia, were among the most frequently observed complications. Hemorrhage also remained a leading direct cause of maternal mortality, especially postpartum hemorrhage, which often requires timely transfusion and surgical intervention. Thromboembolic complications, including pulmonary embolism, were also implicated, reflecting global trends that identify embolic events as increasingly important contributors to maternal mortality. These patterns underscore the multifactorial nature of maternal mortality and the need for a multidisciplinary response.

Finally, the study highlighted issues related to record-keeping and data management. Some variables, including gestational age and referral details, were missing or incompletely recorded for several cases. Accurate documentation is essential for both clinical care and research. The gaps observed in the records indicate a need for improved data collection practices within LASUTH's obstetric unit. Strengthening documentation will support more robust monitoring, facilitate audits, and promote evidence-driven policy decisions.

In summary, the findings reveal that maternal mortality at LASUTH, while relatively low compared to earlier periods, continues to be driven by preventable complications and system-level weaknesses. The determinants identified reflect issues related to late presentation, inadequate referral mechanisms, and delays in recognizing or managing severe obstetric complications.

5.2 Conclusion

Maternal mortality remains a critical public health challenge in Nigeria, although improvements in tertiary-level obstetric care have begun to yield positive outcomes. The findings from LASUTH between 2019 and 2024 demonstrate that while substantial progress has been made, maternal deaths still occur, often resulting from preventable complications that can be effectively managed through timely and coordinated clinical responses.

The study concludes that maternal mortality at LASUTH is shaped by a complex interaction of clinical and systemic factors. Women in their late twenties and early thirties, who would typically be categorized as low-risk, still succumbed to severe

complications, emphasizing that every pregnancy warrants careful monitoring. Late-pregnancy complications accounted for the majority of deaths, demonstrating that the final trimester remains a particularly vulnerable period requiring heightened surveillance.

The significant proportion of maternal deaths among referred patients highlights gaps in the continuum of care. Delays in recognition of complications, inadequate stabilization at referring centers, and inefficient transport systems contribute to poor outcomes. Furthermore, deaths occurring shortly after arrival at LASUTH suggest that many women reach tertiary care facilities at a critical stage when therapeutic interventions may be less effective.

Hypertensive disorders, hemorrhage, sepsis, and thromboembolism remain leading causes of maternal death, consistent with national and global patterns. These findings reinforce the priority areas for clinical focus and policy intervention within maternal health programs. The persistence of these preventable causes indicates that improvements in antenatal care, emergency obstetric protocols, and postpartum monitoring are essential.

The study also concludes that documentation practices require strengthening. Missing information limits accurate case reviews, prevents thorough audits, and restricts the ability of researchers and policymakers to draw comprehensive conclusions.

Improved medical record systems and digital health solutions could greatly enhance the quality of maternity data at LASUTH.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for a multi-level approach that addresses both clinical and systemic challenges. This includes strengthening emergency

obstetric care, enhancing referral networks, improving health worker training, expanding community awareness programs, and ensuring continuous quality improvement in maternity services. Addressing these issues will contribute to sustained reductions in maternal mortality at LASUTH and support national efforts to achieve Sustainable Development Goal targets on maternal health.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1. Strengthen antenatal care services.** Early detection and management of hypertensive disorders and anemia should be prioritized, alongside improved monitoring of high-risk pregnancies.
- 2. Enhance emergency obstetric care capacity.** LASUTH should continue to expand its capacity to manage hemorrhage, eclampsia, sepsis, and thromboembolic events. Regular simulation drills and multidisciplinary case reviews are recommended.
- 3. Improve the referral system.** Clear communication channels between LASUTH and primary or secondary facilities should be established. Standardized referral protocols and rapid transport mechanisms will help reduce delays.
- 4. Engage with Traditional Birth Attendants.** Training and supportive supervision for TBAs can improve timely recognition of complications. Community education should also emphasize the importance of skilled birth attendance.
- 5. Strengthen data management.** LASUTH should adopt standardized digital tools for documentation to ensure accurate and complete maternal health records.

6. Increase public health education. Community-based programs should focus on recognizing danger signs in pregnancy, the importance of early antenatal care, and the need for facility-based delivery.

7. Improve postpartum monitoring. Routine postpartum observations and risk assessment should be strengthened, as many life-threatening complications occur shortly after delivery.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge in several ways:

- 1. Updated empirical data** on maternal mortality trends at LASUTH from 2019 to 2024, offering current insights for policy and planning.
- 2. Identification of key determinants** of maternal mortality within a tertiary hospital setting in Lagos, highlighting hypertensive disorders, hemorrhage, and thromboembolism as persistent threats.
- 3. Analysis of referral patterns**, showing the significant role of external facilities and TBAs in the mortality profile, thereby underscoring systemic gaps in the maternal health continuum.
- 4. Insight into timing of maternal deaths**, particularly deaths occurring soon after admission, which emphasizes the urgency of improving emergency response systems.
- 5. Documentation gaps** that hinder effective case auditing and outcome improvement efforts. By highlighting these weaknesses, the study provides evidence to support investments in digital health information systems.

Collectively, these contributions enhance understanding of maternal mortality dynamics in Lagos State and offer a framework for designing targeted interventions within tertiary care institutions.

5.5 Suggested Areas for Further Research

The following areas are recommended for future research:

1. **A comprehensive multi-facility study** comparing maternal mortality trends across Lagos State to identify inter-institutional variations and best practices.
2. **Qualitative investigations** involving interviews with healthcare workers to understand systemic barriers to timely referral, triage, and emergency intervention.
3. **Community-level studies** exploring cultural, socioeconomic, and behavioral factors that influence late presentation and reliance on Traditional Birth Attendants.
4. **Prospective cohort studies** on high-risk pregnancies to evaluate predictors of adverse outcomes, including hypertension, postpartum hemorrhage, and embolic events.
5. **Evaluation of digital health tools** for improving documentation, case tracking, and clinical decision-making in obstetric care.
6. **Assessment of transport and emergency response systems**, focusing on delays in accessing tertiary care and the effectiveness of ambulance services.

Further research in these areas would deepen understanding of maternal health dynamics in Lagos State and support the development of evidence-based interventions to reduce maternal mortality.